

**UNIVERSITY of
RWANDA**

**Research and postgraduate studies
(RPGS) Unit**

ENHANCING THE USER EXPERIENCE AND ACCESSIBILITY OF MUSIC CULTURAL HERITAGE DIGITAL ARCHIVES.

A human-centred approach to software engineering

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of master's in software engineering

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Declaration

I, Honorine Uwase,
declare that this thesis titled "Enhancing the User Experience and Accessibility of Music Cultural Heritage Digital Archives" is my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree or qualification. I also confirm that I have properly acknowledged and cited all sources of information used in this thesis.

This work was done under the guidance of my supervisors, Dr.Ghislain Maurice Norbert Isabwe and Dr. Ngenzi Alexander, and follows the ethical guidelines set by University of Rwanda for academic research.

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Abstract

Traditional music is an essential part of cultural heritage, yet its accessibility and preservation face significant challenges in the digital era. The main problem lies in the lack of technological solutions that enable broad access to traditional music, limiting community engagement and the ability to share and celebrate cultural identity across generations and geographies. Inconsistent metadata standards and technological barriers frequently limit the efficient preservation and global accessibility of music archives. Efforts to preserve and transmit musical history across generations are further complicated by the fact that many traditional music collections are still at risk of data loss, storage format decay, and a lack of technical experience in preservation approaches. This thesis addresses the challenges by creating an accessible digital archive platform that improves interaction with traditional music heritage archive using a human-centered approach (HCD). The platform maintains an accessible and usable design while guaranteeing data integrity, protection against unauthorised access, and long-term sustainability through the integration of ISO/IEC 27001:2022 security standards. By adopting guidelines for high quality user experience design and following standardized metadata for music archive systems, the results indicate that the designed platform can foster cultural heritage preservation and increase access to traditional music through digital community engagement. However, this thesis acknowledges certain limitations and challenges in developing universally applicable user experience designs that effectively address diverse cultural expectations and technological constraints. Future work can investigate using machine learning techniques for content personalization and improving accessibility in the digital music heritage archive systems.

List of Acronyms

HCD	Human Centered Design
GUI	Graphic User Interface
VUI	Voice User Interface
UX	User Experience
ILAM	International Library of African Music
APMA	Asia Pacific Music Archive
SUS	System Usability Scale
UEQ	User Experience Questionnaire
UI	User Interface
RCHA	Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy
CD	Compact Disk
VR	Virtual reality
AR	Augmented Reality
AI	Artificial intelligence
TV	Television
3D	Three-dimensional
DML	Digital Music Lab
PWAs	Progressive Web Apps
NFSA	National Film and Sound Archive
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
WebXR	Web Extended Reality
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service
OTPs	One-time passcodes
SMS	Short Message Service
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control

ABAC Attribute-Based Access Control

AES Advanced Encryption Standard

TLS/SSL Transport Layer Security/Secure Sockets Layer

WAF Web Application Firewall

SQL Structured Query Language

XSS Cross-site Scripting

IDS/IPS Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems

API Application Programming Interface

NLP Natural Language Processing

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivation

Cultural heritage is important for keeping the identity and traditions of communities alive[1], and music is a big part of this. Traditional music holds stories, rituals, and history that are unique to each culture[2]. But with modern technology and changing times, it has become harder to keep this music safe for future generations[3]. Traditional music is often stored in physical archives, which can get damaged or worn out over time.

With new digital technologies, there is a chance to improve how music is preserved, shared, and accessed. Digital archives are easier to maintain and allow more people to access the music. However, many digital music archives still have problems[3]. Often, they are difficult to use, especially for people who are not familiar with digital tools or who have special needs[4].

This study is motivated by the need to improve how digital music archives work. The goal is to make them easier for people to use while also protecting the music and cultural content. By focusing on how users interact with these archives, the study aims to create a system that is simple, inclusive, and enjoyable to use, so that traditional music can be enjoyed and preserved for years to come.

1.2 Problem Statement

Rwanda's music cultural heritage is an important part of the country's cultural identity and reflects its rich traditions, values, and creativity. However, this unique heritage is in danger of being lost. Many recordings and materials are not available in digital form and are scattered across different people, organizations, and places. This makes it difficult to keep them safe or ensure they are preserved for future generations. Over time, the risk of losing this music increases, especially as older formats degrade or become unusable[5].

Some efforts have been made to preserve Rwanda's traditional music. For example, more than 4,000 sound recordings were brought from the [6]Belgium Africa-Museum to Rwanda to help preserve them[7][8]. These recordings, which were originally for research, have been changed into digital files to stop them from being lost, as older recordings can easily get damaged. However, many of these digital files are not well organized or documented, limiting their availability to only a few people. This makes it difficult to access and use them for learning, research, or enjoyment.

Another effort is the significant step taken by the government of Rwanda in establishing the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy (RCHA)[9]in 2020, with one of its main responsibilities being to collect, preserve, and exhibit objects of national cultural heritage, including music heritage. In addition, many other recordings of Rwanda's traditional music are still stored in older physical formats like tapes, Compact Disk (CD)s, and vinyl records. These formats are prone to physical

damage, such as scratches, breaks, or deterioration over time[5]. The challenges of poor collection mechanisms, inadequate documentation, limited access, and the vulnerability of physical formats highlight the need to prioritize the preservation and accessibility of Rwanda's cultural heritage.

1.3 Study Objectives

1.3.1 General Objective

To design and develop a digital archive system for Rwandan music cultural heritage that is intuitive, engaging, and accessible to a diverse user base.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. Ensure the platform meets the needs of diverse users, including those with disabilities.
2. Apply user-centered design principles to ensure a seamless and intuitive user experience.
3. Digitize and organize traditional Rwandan music, ensuring it is protected for future generations.
4. Provide tools and resources that facilitate the use of the archive by researchers and educators.
5. Protect user information and archived materials from unauthorized access.

1.4 Hypotheses and Research Questions

1. **RQ1:** What are the most effective approaches for preserving music cultural heritage to ensure its accessibility to future generations?
2. **RQ2:** How can a usable and accessible digital archive system be designed to effectively preserve cultural heritage of music?
3. **RQ3:** What are the essential data security measures and web accessibility guidelines required to ensure the integrity and accessibility of cultural heritage of music in a digital archive system?

1.5 Study Scope

This study focuses on improving the user experience and accessibility of digital archives that manage Rwanda's musical cultural heritage. The goal is to create a digital archive system that makes it easy for people to access and enjoy music heritage while also protecting it for the future. The study will focus on designing a system that is easy to use, accessible to everyone and secure to ensure that music is preserved safely[10].

The project will explore the best ways to store and protect music heritage in a digital format, ensuring it remains available for upcoming generations. It will also test the system to make sure it is simple to use, even for people who are not very familiar with technology. The security of the system will also be tested to ensure that music and other cultural materials are safe from unauthorized access or loss[11].

Throughout the study, a human-centered approach[12] will be used, which means that design and evaluation will consider the needs and challenges of users to create a system that works for them[13]. Ultimately, this study aims to improve the way cultural music heritage is preserved and accessed in a user-friendly and secure way[14].

1.6 Limitation and constraints

There are several limitations, including incomplete or missing metadata in the digital archive, which affects how well users can search and interact with the content[15]. The system's accessibility may also be limited due to the internet access required, and it might not support all types of disabilities. For example, users who are blind may not be able to access visual content, and users with hearing impairments might face difficulties with audio content.

The project also relies on existing technology infrastructure, which may not support all the advanced features needed for an optimal user experience. Implementing accessibility solutions and improving the user experience may be restricted by the current technology available. Lastly, copyright laws and data protection regulations[16] may limit how content can be accessed and shared.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to make music cultural heritage more accessible and easier to use for everyone. By creating a digital archive system that is simple, secure, and user-friendly, this study will help preserve important cultural music for future generations. It will also ensure that people, including researchers, students, and the general public, will easily access and enjoy this music. This study will also provide valuable insights into designing digital systems that meet the needs of users, helping improve how cultural heritage is stored and shared. Ultimately, the findings will contribute to better preserving and appreciating music cultural heritage in a digital age.

1.8 Organization of the Study

The study is organized to guide the reader through a clear progression of ideas. The Introduction chapter provides the background and motivation for the study, presents the problem statement, outlines the study objectives, and defines the scope. It also explains the study's limitations and significance.

The Literature Review chapter examines the role of technology in preserving cultural heritage through music. It discusses challenges in digital music archives, such as user interface issues and gaps in existing systems. The review explores how modern web technologies can improve these archives, focusing on Rwanda's music heritage. It also covers data security measures and ethical concerns related to digital preservation.

In the Research Methodology chapter, the study explains the data gathering methods, which include both qualitative and quantitative approaches, as well as the human-centered design approach guiding the research. This chapter also describes user testing and the tools used to evaluate the system.

The chapter on analysis, design, and implementation will provide an overview of system and requirements analysis, user stories, and task models, followed by the system design through prototypes. It will also cover system architecture, the technologies used, the implementation process, security measures, integration and testing, and conclude with user interface details for exploring archives and discovering artists.

The study concludes with the Results and Analysis chapter, where the findings are presented, followed by the Conclusion and Recommendations chapter, which summarizes the study and suggests areas for future research or improvements.

1.9 Conclusion

The introduction chapter sets the stage for this study by highlighting the importance of preserving music cultural heritage and the challenges faced in the digital era. It outlines the motivation behind enhancing user experience and accessibility in digital archives, with a specific focus on a human-centered approach to software design. The study's objectives, scope, and significance have been clearly established, providing a foundation for exploring how technology can improve the preservation and accessibility of traditional music. The following chapters will build upon this introduction to present the methodology, analysis, and results that aim to address the identified problems and offer practical solutions.

Chapter 2

State Of The Art

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the literature and state-of-the-art technologies related to the preservation of music cultural heritage. The purpose of the literature review is to explore existing systems, methods, and technologies that have been utilized in digital archiving and evaluate their effectiveness in meeting the needs of diverse user groups.

By analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of these systems, this review aims to identify gaps in the current landscape and highlight opportunities for innovation, particularly in the context of enhancing user experience and accessibility. Reviewing existing approaches is critical as it lays the foundation for designing a more effective and inclusive system tailored to the preservation of Rwandan music heritage. This analysis also helps in understanding the broader challenges and motivations behind digital cultural preservation efforts.

The scope of this review extends to exploring key concepts in user experience design, accessibility standards, and technological solutions used in similar digital archiving projects worldwide. By doing so, it provides a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-the-art and informs the design and development of the proposed system.

2.2 Cultural Heritage Preservation

Preserving cultural heritage means protecting and maintaining the tangible and intangible parts of a community's identity so that it can be passed on to future generations. This includes activities such as documenting, conserving, restoring, and digitally archiving cultural items such as artifacts, music, dance, language, and traditions[17].

When it comes to music, preservation involves recording audio, documenting lyrics, maintaining instruments, and capturing the stories behind the music. This is especially important in places like Rwanda, where music plays a vital role in storytelling, sharing customs, and keeping cultural identity alive[18].

In the context of music cultural heritage, preservation involves capturing and storing audio recordings, lyrics, instruments, and related narratives to maintain the historical and cultural significance of these traditions. This is especially important in places like Rwanda, where music plays a vital role in storytelling, sharing customs, and keeping cultural identity alive. identity[17].

Cultural heritage preservation is important for many reasons. It helps communities and nations protect their unique history and traditions, keeping their identity alive. By preserving cultural heritage, future generations can learn about their past and understand their roots, which is vital for education. It also brings people together by highlighting shared values and traditions, promoting unity and understanding among different groups. Additionally, it plays a key role in maintaining

diversity by celebrating cultural differences, which helps balance the effects of globalization. This ensures that various cultures continue to thrive and are not lost over time.

Figure 2.1: Overview explanation of Cultural Heritage Preservation

In today’s digital world, preserving cultural heritage has expanded to include digital archives and databases[19]. These tools make cultural resources easier to access and help protect fragile materials through digitization. This is particularly important for intangible heritage like music, which risks being lost as physical media decay and oral traditions fade.

[20]By using technology and designing user-friendly digital tools, preservation efforts can reach more people and keep cultural treasures relevant and accessible in a fast-changing world.

2.2.1 The Role of Music in Preserving Cultural Traditions

Music brings people together, breaking language and cultural barriers[21][17]. It is a powerful way to protect and share traditions. Cultural heritage includes the customs, beliefs, and practices that make every community unique. But modernization and globalization can put these traditions at risk[22]. Music helps keep cultural identity alive, promotes understanding between cultures, and passes traditions on to the next generation. Traditional music teaches young people about their history and roots and is often used in schools and communities to celebrate and share heritage.

In the world, music plays an important role in preserving traditions[17]. In India, classical music such as Hindustani and Carnatic keeps centuries-old traditions alive. In China, traditional instruments such as the guzheng help maintain cultural practices. In Africa, drumming and dancing are central to many communities, while in Latin America, styles such as salsa and samba preserve cultural heritage. In Rwanda, traditional music reflects the country’s history and values through songs and dances that tell stories and celebrate important moments.

In Rwanda, music is a big part of the country’s culture and history. The Rwanda Cultural and Heritage Academy (RCHA) [9] recently celebrated World Day for Audiovisual Heritage with an exhibition of over 4,000 traditional songs[6]. These songs, include Imbyino (storytelling songs), Indirimbo z’abashumba b’inka (pastoral songs), and Ivyivugo (self-praising songs). They were performed using traditional instruments like the Inanga (harp), Umuduri (musical bow), and In-goma (drum) [7]. The event showed how rich Rwanda’s musical heritage is and encouraged young people to embrace and learn from it. By preserving and sharing traditional music, Rwandans can keep their culture alive for future generations.

2.2.2 Challenges in Preserving Traditional Music in the Modern World

Traditional music faces many problems today. People moving to cities breaks down the communities where traditional music is important. Modern lifestyles make people less interested in these traditions and global trends push people away from local music. Money problems also make it hard for traditional musicians to earn a living. Younger generations are losing touch with older music traditions because they do not learn from older people [23].

Globalization makes things worse by showing people popular global music through TV and the Internet, which pushes local music aside. Technology makes it easier to share music, but this reduces live performances. Mixing different styles of music and using mass-produced instruments can change traditional music and its sound [19]. Despite these challenges, technology offers promising avenues for the preservation and revitalization of traditional music. Digital archiving [24] enables the recording and storage of traditional music, making it accessible to a global audience and ensuring its longevity. Educational platforms can integrate traditional music into curricula, fostering appreciation and practice among younger generations. Interactive applications and virtual reality experiences [25] can immerse users in the cultural contexts of traditional music, improving understanding and engagement [10]. In addition, collaborations between technologists and traditional musicians can lead to innovative projects that respect and preserve the essence of traditional music while adapting it to contemporary formats.

It is crucial that these technological interventions are implemented with cultural sensitivity and ethical considerations[4]. Ensuring that communities have control over how their music is shared and used protects against exploitation and maintains the music's integrity. By thoughtfully integrating modern technology with human-centered design principles [12] [26], we can create sustainable methods to preserve and celebrate traditional music, ensuring it remains a vibrant part of our global cultural landscape.

2.3 Technology in Cultural Heritage Preservation

Role of Technology in Cultural Heritage Preservation

Technology plays a vital role in protecting and sharing cultural heritage, using innovative tools to preserve traditions and artifacts for future generations[27]. As modernization, climate change, and conflicts put cultural heritage at risk, technology provides practical and creative ways to ensure these treasures are not lost.

Digitization is one of the most impactful methods[28]. By converting physical items like artifacts, books, and music into digital formats, fragile or rare items are preserved while being made widely accessible. Digital archives and libraries allow researchers, educators, and the public to explore cultural heritage without damaging the originals.

Virtual reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) offer immersive ways to experience cultural heritage. VR creates fully virtual environments where users can "visit" cultural sites or explore historical events as if they were there. AR overlays digital information onto the real world, such as showing how an ancient ruin looked in its prime. These tools are especially helpful for endangered or remote sites, preserving their memory and making them accessible to everyone[25].

Artificial intelligence (AI) brings advanced capabilities to cultural preservation. AI can restore damaged artifacts, fill in missing parts of historical texts, or even recreate music and artwork that has been lost[29]. Machine learning, a type of AI, organizes large collections of cultural data, making it easier to search, analyze, and interpret, saving time and effort for researchers. 3D printing offers a way to replicate artifacts and historical structures with incredible accuracy[30].

This technology allows museums to create replicas of items too fragile or valuable to display, letting people interact with them without risking the originals. It is also used to reconstruct destroyed cultural sites, helping people understand and appreciate their significance.

Figure 2.2: Technologies in cultural heritage

Social media and online platforms have revolutionized how cultural heritage is shared and promoted[31]. Communities can showcase their traditions, festivals, and crafts to a global audience, fostering greater appreciation and understanding. Platforms like YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok allow traditional musicians, dancers, and storytellers to reach people worldwide, ensuring their art stays relevant.

High-quality audio and video recordings are crucial for preserving intangible cultural heritage, such as oral traditions, dances, and performances. These technologies ensure that even traditions not written down can be recorded and passed on to future generations.

By integrating these tools, technology makes cultural heritage accessible, engaging, and secure, helping the world celebrate and protect its rich diversity.

2.3.1 Modern Web Technologies in Digital Music Archives

The advancement of web technologies has significantly transformed digital music archives, addressing challenges related to preservation, accessibility, and engagement[32]. This paper examines the role of modern web technologies in enhancing the storage, organization, and dissemination of traditional music collections.

Web-based music learning platforms, such as EarSketch [33], integrate music creation with programming, fostering both cultural preservation and creativity[34]. The use of big data in projects

such as the Digital Music Lab (DML) [35] allows researchers to analyze large-scale music collections, uncovering historical patterns and trends. Additionally, interactive digital libraries facilitate collaborative archiving [36], enabling communities to contribute metadata and enrich musical heritage records.

2.3.2 User Interface and Interaction Challenges in Web Technologies

The evolution of digital music archives has transformed the way users access, explore, and interact with cultural heritage [37]. Initially, these archives consisted of simple, static websites with basic navigation, making it difficult for users to engage with traditional music collections [35] [38] meaningfully. Over time, advancements in web technologies introduced dynamic interfaces, multimedia integration, and interactive search functionalities. However, despite these improvements, significant challenges persist in ensuring an intuitive and inclusive user experience. Without well-structured UI and interaction design, digital music archives risk becoming complex and inaccessible, discouraging users from engaging with their rich content [39].

Figure 2.3: DEKKMMA website as bad example of UI and Interaction challenges

One of the primary challenges in UI design for digital music archives is accessibility [40]. Many traditional music platforms struggle to provide features that accommodate diverse users, including those with visual or hearing impairments [26]. Insufficient support for screen readers, poor contrast ratios, and non-adaptive layouts limit the usability of these platforms. Additionally, the diversity of file formats and metadata structures [24] creates inconsistencies in how music is presented, making it difficult for users to browse and retrieve relevant content seamlessly. Furthermore, the lack of standardization in media playback [33] tools across different devices exacerbates the issue, leading to fragmented user experiences.

A clear example of poor UI [38] and interaction design in digital music archives is the DEKKMMA website [8]. The homepage lacks clear navigation, leaving users uncertain about where to click. The absence of intuitive buttons for playing songs or reading about musical instruments increases the likelihood of users abandoning the site. This poor design results in high dropout rates as users struggle to engage with the archive's content effectively. Without clear guidance, even those

interested in traditional music may find the experience frustrating, ultimately defeating the purpose of digital preservation.

Technological advancements offer potential solutions to these challenges, yet they also introduce new complexities. The rise of Progressive Web Apps (PWAs) [41] and WebAssembly can enhance performance and accessibility [42], but their adoption in digital music archives remains limited. AI-driven personalization and recommendation systems [29] present an opportunity to improve user engagement by curating content based on listening behavior, yet they must balance automation with cultural authenticity. Immersive web technologies, such as WebXR [43], could revolutionize interaction by simulating live traditional performances and providing deeper emotional connections to archived music. However, implementing these innovations requires careful consideration of cultural sensitivity and data ethics to ensure that traditional music is not reduced to a purely algorithm-driven experience. By integrating user-centered design principles with emerging web technologies, digital music archives can create more accessible, engaging, and culturally respectful platforms that preserve and promote traditional music heritage effectively [44].

2.3.3 Data Security Measures for Digital Music Archives

The Importance of Security in Music Cultural Heritage Archives

The preservation of music cultural heritage in digital archives is very important for ensuring long-term accessibility and safeguarding historically significant recordings from cyber threats, unauthorized access, and data loss [45]. These archives often contain rare musical pieces, cultural performances, and sensitive historical materials that require a secure and controlled environment to prevent tampering, theft, or unauthorized distribution.

Implementing robust security measures is particularly important because digital music archives face increasing risks, including [46]:

1. Data breaches, where unauthorized entities gain access to stored materials.
2. Cyberattacks, such as ransomware and Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks, which can make the archive inaccessible or permanently damage stored content.
3. Unauthorized modifications, where digital content is altered, deleted, or misrepresented.
4. Intellectual property theft, where copyrighted works are illegally distributed or misused without proper attribution.

To address these concerns, modern web application security technologies are used to enhance the integrity, confidentiality, and accessibility of archived music while ensuring legitimate users (e.g., researchers, educators, and cultural institutions) can access relevant resources.

Authentication and Access Control Mechanisms

To prevent unauthorized access, digital archives implement authentication and access control mechanisms that ensure only authorized users can retrieve, modify, or manage archived content.

Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)

MFA strengthens login security by requiring users to verify their identity using multiple methods, including passwords (knowledge-based authentication), one-time passcodes (OTPs) sent via email, SMS, or authentication apps, and biometric verification (fingerprint or facial recognition). By requiring multiple authentication steps, MFA reduces the risk of credential theft and enhances user

identity verification.[47]

Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)

A hierarchical access control system ensures that users only have access to the resources necessary for their roles. RBAC categorizes users into roles such as general users (who can access public materials but cannot modify metadata), researchers and educators (who can retrieve detailed metadata and historical context), and administrators and archivists (who can upload, modify, and remove content while managing security settings). ABAC further enhances security by applying context-aware rules, such as restricting access based on geolocation or institutional affiliation, and limiting availability of sensitive materials based on time-sensitive permissions (e.g., temporary access for specific research projects)[45]. By integrating RBAC and ABAC, digital archives ensure that materials are accessible only to authorized users while maintaining compliance with copyright and ethical considerations.

Encryption for Data Protection

Encryption protects stored and transmitted data from being intercepted or altered. AES-256 encryption secures music recordings, metadata, and user credentials, ensuring that even if an attacker gains access to the system, the data remains unreadable without proper decryption keys. Database encryption also ensures that user information, research logs, and content annotations are protected from internal and external threats. For data transmission, TLS 1.3 (Transport Layer Security) encrypts all data transfers between users and the archive server, protecting against man-in-the-middle attacks. SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) certificates verify the authenticity of digital archive platforms, preventing users from being redirected to fraudulent versions of the archive. [47]These encryption mechanisms guarantee that archived materials remain confidential and intact, regardless of where or how they are accessed.

Web Application Security and Threat Mitigation

Digital music archives, as online platforms, are vulnerable to various cyber threats. To mitigate risks, advanced web application security measures are implemented. A cloud-based Web Application Firewall (WAF) monitors and filters incoming traffic, blocking malicious activities such as SQL injection attacks, Cross-site scripting (XSS) attacks, and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. By analyzing incoming requests in real-time, a WAF protects the archive from unauthorized intrusions and automated bot attacks. Additionally, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) analyze user activity to identify unusual patterns, such as multiple failed login attempts, while Intrusion Prevention Systems (IPS) actively block suspicious activities. Together, these systems ensure that cyber threats are detected and mitigated before they can compromise data integrity and system availability[46].

Secure API Access and Rate Limiting

Many digital archives expose APIs for searching, retrieving, and modifying metadata, making it essential to implement secure API policies to prevent abuse and unauthorized data extraction. OAuth-based API authentication ensures that only authorized applications interact with the archive, while API Gateway Security filters incoming requests to block unauthorized or malicious queries. Additionally, rate limiting and throttling prevent excessive requests from bots attempting to scrape content. By securing APIs, digital archives maintain controlled data access, effectively preventing

automated attacks while ensuring researchers can efficiently retrieve the materials they need[48].

Ethical Considerations in Digital Archive Security

Beyond technological solutions, ethical considerations must be addressed when securing cultural heritage materials.

Culturally sensitive recordings should be accessible only to authorized researchers or members of relevant communities. [47]Transparent access policies must define who can access data, under what conditions, and how long access is granted. Consent-based sharing ensures that contributors, artists, and communities retain control over their heritage materials. By embedding ethical principles into security frameworks, digital music archives uphold both digital integrity and cultural respect.

Ensuring data security in digital music archives requires a multi-layered security framework that incorporates[45]:

Strong authentication and access control mechanisms (MFA, RBAC, ABAC). Robust encryption techniques (AES-256 for storage, TLS for transmission). Advanced web security tools (WAF, IDS/IPS, secure API access[48]). Blockchain-based integrity tracking to prevent tampering and verify authenticity. These measures collectively protect archived materials from unauthorized access, cyber threats, and ethical misuse, ensuring long-term preservation and controlled accessibility for researchers and educators[46].

Future research should explore AI-driven security automation and privacy-enhancing technologies to further strengthen digital music heritage protection

2.4 Existing Digital Music Archives

Digital music archives play an important role in preserving cultural music and making it accessible to a global audience. These archives help protect valuable musical traditions and allow users to explore music from different countries and cultures. Some notable examples include the British Council Music Archive[49] in the UK, which offers playlists, artist profiles, and event details to showcase British music. In Australia, the National Film and Sound Archive (NFSA)[50] stores recordings, oral stories, and soundtracks to share Australia's rich musical history. Similarly, Smithsonian Folkways Recordings[51] in the US collects folk and traditional music from around the world, providing educational resources for research and learning.

In addition to these, there are archives dedicated to preserving the music of specific regions. The International Library of African Music (ILAM)[18] in South Africa focuses on African music recordings, helping preserve and research African music traditions. The Music Finland Archive in Finland[52] highlights Finnish music, especially jazz, and helps connect Finnish artists with the global music scene. The Europeana Music Collection[53] provides access to music resources from European libraries and museums, including old sheet music and historical recordings, helping to preserve European music history. The Internet Archive - Music[54] Collection offers free access to live performances, podcasts, and recordings from a wide range of genres. Discogs[55] allows users to catalog and trade physical music like records and CDs, offering a digital platform for preserving music collections.

In the United States, the American Memory Archive[56] at the Library of Congress shares historical recordings, sheet music, and multimedia, offering a window into the country's music history. Lastly, the Asia Pacific Music Archive (APMA)[57] focuses on music from Asia and the Pacific, sharing traditional and modern recordings from the region. These are just a few examples among many digital music archives around the world. While these platforms provide valuable resources,

there remains potential for improvement in user experience and accessibility, which is the focus of ongoing research in this field.

2.4.1 Gaps in Existing Digital Music Archives

Digital music archives are important for saving and sharing cultural heritage, but many of them are not easy to use[20]. For example, Smithsonian Folkways Recordings[51] has a large collection of folk and traditional music, including some from Rwanda. However, the website is hard to navigate. The search and filtering options are limited, making it hard to find specific content. Also, the mix of articles, music, and educational materials is disorganized, causing confusion. Even though the platform wants to promote underrepresented cultures, these design problems make it harder for many people to use. Other platforms, like the International Library of African Music (ILAM)[18], have similar issues. The search tool often gives inconsistent results, and the music is not sorted by country, genre, or instrument, making it hard to explore. The website is also not mobile-friendly, which means not everyone can use it. Other archives, like the American Memory Collection[56] from the Library of Congress and the Free Music Archive, also have problems with navigation and lack important features like filters.

The British Council’s Music platform[49], The Internet Archive-Music[54] , and the Music Finland Archive also face usability issues. These platforms, while holding important collections, have their own challenges. [49]The British Council’s site lacks clear navigation and can be confusing to use. [54]The Internet Archive - Music has a vast collection, but its search function is not effective, and finding specific content is not straightforward. [52]The Music Finland Archive, while showcasing Finnish music, is similarly hard to navigate, and its categorization of music could be better organized. These problems show that many digital music archives, despite having valuable content, need improvements to make them more user-friendly.

These issues across different platforms highlight the need for improvement, organization, and design to make digital music archives easier to use. Fixing these problems will help these platforms better preserve and sharing of music with people around the world.

2.4.2 Rwanda’s Music Heritage: Gaps, Limitations, and Risks

Rwanda has a rich musical heritage, but there are still challenges in preserving and sharing it. In October 2021, over 4,000 audio recordings of Rwandan traditional music, recorded between the 1950s and 1990s, were transferred from the AfricaM useum in Belgium[8] to the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy[9]. These recordings were originally in analog formats, but they have now been converted into digital files as part of the SHARE programme. The goal of the SHARE programme is to preserve this music and share it while also helping local museums in Rwanda improve how they manage their collections[6].

These digitized recordings have been stored at the Ethnographic Museum in Huye[58]. While this is a step forward, the music is not yet easily accessible to the public. Right now, the recordings are available through exhibitions and social media, but there is no simple, centralized digital platform where people can easily search for and explore these musical archives.

While the SHARE programme has made progress by converting these analog recordings into digital formats[6], there is still a gap in organizing and presenting the music in an accessible way. The recordings contain valuable information like titles, locations, and details about their ritual significance, but without features like search filters or interactive tools, it’s difficult for users to explore the collection.

Although efforts are being made to preserve these archives and even collaborate with contemporary artists to reinterpret Rwanda’s music[6][58], there is still a need for a long-term, self-sufficient digital platform that will make this heritage available to the public. More work is needed to not

only digitize these recordings but also to create a user-friendly system that allows people to easily access and engage with Rwanda's rich musical traditions.

while Rwanda has made important progress in converting its analog music archives into digital formats, there is still a need to improve how these resources are organized and presented online so that they are more accessible and easier to use for everyone.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

This chapter explains how the research was done, focusing on the methods used and why they were chosen. These methods were selected to achieve the main goal: making a digital archive system for music heritage easier and more enjoyable for everyone to use, including researchers, archivists, and the general public.

The study uses a human-centered design approach [59], focusing on what users need and how they interact with the system. The research looks at ways to improve access to music heritage resources by listening to user feedback.

The chapter also explains how the data was collected through interviews, surveys, and user testing to ensure the results are accurate and meaningful. It provides a detailed breakdown of the testing process, starting with understanding user needs in the early stages and evaluating the system's ease of use and accessibility in the later phases.

These efforts aim to build a system that effectively addresses user needs while making the exploration of music heritage more enjoyable and engaging.

3.1 Qualitative Data Collection Methods

Qualitative data methods [60] are research techniques used to explore and understand people's behaviors, experiences, motivations, and opinions. Unlike quantitative methods, which rely on numerical data and statistical analysis, qualitative methods focus on gathering non-numerical descriptive insights [61] through direct engagement with participants. These methods help researchers uncover patterns, themes, and deeper meanings behind human interactions, making them particularly useful in fields like user experience (UX) research, human-centred design, and social sciences.

3.1.1 Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with participants who had experience or interest in using digital archives. This method provided a balance between structured guidance and flexibility, allowing participants to freely share their thoughts while ensuring that the conversation remained relevant to the research objectives. The interview process encouraged participants to reflect on their experiences, articulate their challenges, and suggest improvements.

A diverse group of participants was selected to capture a range of perspectives, including individuals with varying levels of expertise in digital archives. An interview guide had been prepared to ensure clarity and relevance, containing open-ended questions that promoted meaningful discussion. This approach allowed the collection of rich and qualitative data [60] that provided insight into user preferences and areas for improvement.

3.1.2 Observations

Observations were made to understand how music archives are manually managed and how participants used the newly designed system. We visited the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy (RCHA), exhibitions, and the Kandt house Museum to observe how they manage music archives manually. These visits helped gather valuable information to design an improved user experience for the new system.

I also observed the participants during usability testing to see how they interacted with the newly designed system. Participants were asked to complete tasks while I was taking notes on their actions and expressions. This helped identify any problems they faced and which features were most useful. These observations gave me important information to improve the system design.

3.1.3 Surveys

Surveys were used to collect feedback from a larger group of users, providing both quantitative and qualitative information on their experiences. The surveys were aimed at assessing users' opinions on usability, accessibility, and general satisfaction with the digital archive system.

The surveys included the System Usability Scale (SUS) and the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ).

User experience questionnaire(UEQ)

In this study, a customized version of the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) was used to collect feedback from participants about their experience with the system. The UEQ [62] is a tool designed to measure different aspects of user experience, including satisfaction, ease of use, and overall impression. However, a customized version was created to tailor the questionnaire to the specific context of this study, focusing on elements relevant to the multimodal interface and its interaction with users [63].

The UEQ looked at these important things:

- Attractiveness: Do users like or dislike the product?
- Perspicuity: Is it easy to understand and learn how to use the product?
- Efficiency: Can users do their tasks without wasting time or effort? Does it work fast?
- Dependability: Do users feel in control? Is the product safe and reliable?
- Stimulation: Is the product exciting and fun to use? Does it keep users motivated?
- Novelty: Is the design creative and interesting to users?

The reason for using the UEQ, and particularly the customized version, was to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the participants' emotional reactions, satisfaction, and thoughts about the system. Unlike the SUS, which focuses primarily on usability, the UEQ allowed the study to dive deeper into subjective experiences, capturing both positive and negative perceptions. This helped to identify areas where the system met users' expectations and where further improvements were needed to enhance the overall user experience.

System usability scale(SUS)

In this study, the System Usability Scale (SUS) was used to assess the usability of the system. SUS is a well-established and widely recognized tool for measuring how easy and user-friendly a system is. It consists of 10 questions that participants answer based on their experience with the system, which results in a score that ranges from 0 to 100[64].

The reason for using SUS in this study was to gather quantitative data on the system's usability. SUS is simple, quick, and provides a benchmark for comparing results across different systems. It has been proven to effectively highlight usability issues and is valuable for understanding how users perceive the system's ease of use. By including SUS, the study ensured that usability was evaluated in a standardized way, complementing other qualitative methods such as interviews and observations.

3.1.4 literature review

The research also looked at current music archive systems to understand how they work. This included studying both digital and manual systems used for music preservation. In particular, research focused on how music archives are managed manually at the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy (RCHA)[9]. By examining how the RCHA handles music archives without digital tools, I aimed to learn about the challenges they face and how a digital system might improve their work. This helped to understand the gap between traditional methods and modern digital solutions in music heritage management

3.1.5 Data Analysis

The data collected from interviews, observations, and surveys has been carefully analyzed to uncover patterns, themes, and areas for improvement. For interviews and observations, the analysis involved grouping responses into categories based on recurring themes, following a qualitative approach similar to grounded theory[60]. This process ensured that the findings were organized and meaningful.

Survey data was analyzed using basic statistical methods to identify trends and preferences among the participants. [61]Qualitative responses from open-ended survey questions have been reviewed to highlight user suggestions and unique insights. Together, these methods provided a comprehensive view of how users interacted with the digital archive and what could be improved.

3.1.6 Ensuring Validity and Reliability

To ensure that the study produced accurate and reliable results, several measures have been taken. Participants have been carefully selected to include individuals who could provide relevant and meaningful feedback. The research process, including data collection methods and procedures, has been clearly documented to maintain consistency and transparency.

Triangulation has been used to cross-check findings from interviews, observations, and surveys, ensuring that the results were robust and credible. This multi-method approach helped validate the findings by confirming patterns observed across different data sources.

By combining these methods, the study aimed to understand user needs comprehensively and provide actionable recommendations for enhancing the design and usability of music cultural heritage digital archives.

3.2 Participant recruitment

Figure 3.1: Participant Demographics and Background Summary

As shown in Figure 3.1, 10 participants were recruited to ensure a mix of relevant skills, knowledge, and diverse perspectives. The group included one UX/Design expert, one UX designer, three traditional music artists, Three individuals working in the field of music heritage conservation, and two individuals with general interest in digital archives. The participants' ages ranged from 25 to 54, with a gender balance of four women and six men.

The participants were chosen because their skills and backgrounds supported the study's goals. UX/Design experts provided insights on usability, while music artists and heritage workers offered cultural and historical perspectives. General participants helped ensure the system was accessible to a wider audience.

Initially, participants contributed to gathering requirements by sharing ideas about how the system should work. Later, they provided feedback on usability, user experience, and ease of use during testing and evaluation.

Although four additional individuals helped shape the system's early design by providing input on their expectations, needs, and suggestions for a better user experience, they were not involved in usability testing and evaluation. These individuals are not shown in Figure 3.1 and did not contribute to the findings or results of the study. Only the main 10 participants were involved in both the early and later stages of the study

3.3 Human-centered design Approach

The Human-centered Design (HCD)[12] process places the user at the center of the design process, ensuring that the final product meets their needs and preferences, thereby enhancing user satisfaction. With human-centered design, people are involved in the design of products and services right from the start. Human-centered Design concentrates on the product users and where and how they will use the product. This user-experience(UX) methodology is guided by a profound understanding of users' needs, preferences, and behaviors, ensuring that the final product aligns with their requirements and enhances user satisfaction[20]. This approach involves several key activities. It begins with understanding and specifying the context of use, ensuring a clear understand of the environment and conditions in which the archive will be utilized. This is followed by specifying the user requirements, identifying the needs and preferences of potential users. Subsequently, design solutions are produced to meet these requirements, creating a system tailored to user needs.

Finally, the design is evaluated against the requirements to ensure it meets the specified objectives and provides the desired user experience.

Figure 3.2: The four activities of human-centered design

3.3.1 Understand and Specify the context of use

The study applied the PACT (People, Activities, Context, Technology) framework to thoroughly identify and understand stakeholders and their needs, with findings drawn from extensive user research and requirement-gathering activities.

People involved in the system were identified through interviews, focus groups, and workshops conducted at Kigali Cultural Village. These efforts highlighted the different user groups, including educators, archivists, researchers, artists, and the general public. Each group has unique roles and expectations, with further details provided in Chapter 4. Additionally, key institutions were identified as stakeholders, such as the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy[9] and the National Museum of Rwanda.

Activities supported by the system were defined through direct task observations at the Rwanda National Museum and semi-structured interviews, where workflows like playlist creation and archive management were identified. Reviews of documents and artifacts provided additional insights into traditional preservation practices. Evaluations of existing online music archive systems informed the selection of features and processes for the platform. These activities range from general users browsing and streaming music to administrators managing tracks and artist profiles.

The context of use was explored by examining how and where users interact with the system. Observations and interviews highlighted the need for flexibility, accessibility, and overall user experience. Users were found to engage with the system on various devices, which necessitated a responsive design. Workshops emphasized the linguistic diversity of users, driving the need for a multilingual interface. Additionally, stakeholder feedback highlighted the importance of compliance with GDPR and WCAG 2.1 standards to ensure data protection.

Technological requirements were identified through focus group discussions and evaluations of

existing platforms. Participants prioritized responsive design, scalability to accommodate future growth, and modular maintenance for system reliability. Security concerns voiced by stakeholders led to the integration of encryption using TLS/SSL[46]

By integrating valuable inputs from observations, interviews, focus groups, and existing online music archive platforms, the PACT framework guided the creation of a user-centered system designed to meet the diverse needs of its users while remaining culturally and technologically adaptable. Detailed findings can be found in Chapter 4, which covers system analysis, design, and implementation.

3.3.2 Specifying The User Requirement

As part of the Human-Centered Design (HCD) process, defining user requirements is important in making sure the system is intuitive, accessible, and meets users' expectations[12].

To archive this, the Volere snow card method was used to clearly list both the essential features and overall qualities of the system. Functional requirements describe the all actions the system must perform, while non-functional requirements focus on how the system should work, such as its ease of use, speed, security, and ability to grow.

The user requirements were based on information gathered from different participants, ensuring the system meets the needs of a wide range of users, including researchers, archivists, artists, educators, and the general public. This approach helps the system address the needs of each group. The use of Volere snow cards ensures that both the functional and non-functional aspects of the system are carefully examined and clearly defined[65]. A full list of all the user requirements and corresponding Volere snow cards can be found in chapter 4.

By gathering and analyzing these requirements, the system will be designed to better meet user expectations, making the digital cultural heritage archive more effective and user-friendly.

3.3.3 Produce design solutions

The design process focused on creating solutions that met user needs by following a clear and structured approach. Several methods were used, including creating a simple plan of how the system should work (conceptual model), breaking down tasks into smaller, manageable steps (Hierarchical Task Analysis or HTA), and developing both preliminary and detailed prototypes. The involvement of UI/UX design experts, archivists, artists, and traditional music lovers at every stage added significant value, ensuring that the system was not only user-friendly but also aligned with best practices in design, archival management, and the unique needs of those passionate about traditional music.

The conceptual model was a high-level plan that showed how users—such as music enthusiasts, archivists, artists, and traditional music lovers would interact with the system. It outlined tasks like organizing playlists, searching for music, and exploring the archive, along with how the system would respond to these actions. This model helped visualize the system's structure and provided a blueprint for its design. Diagram and more details about conceptual model can be found in the Conceptual Model subsection of Chapter.

The HTA broke down tasks into small steps to ensure that every action a user might take, such as typing a search term, applying filters, or playing a track, was simple and logical. This method highlighted areas where users might face challenges and allowed for the design of workflows that minimized confusion and effort. The collaboration with participants helped refine these tasks to

ensure the system will be intuitive for both casual users and professionals managing digital music archives. Diagram and more details about HTA can also be found in the Hierarchical Task Analysis subsection of Chapter 4.

To test and refine these ideas, low-fidelity prototypes simple paper sketches of the interface were created. These sketches showed basic layouts, navigation paths, and the overall flow of the system. They were quick and easy to update based on feedback. Once the initial ideas were improved, high-fidelity prototype using Figma were developed. it is an interactive, detailed designs allowed users to click through screens and experience the system as if it were fully functional. The complete analysis, along with figures related to the prototypes, will be detailed in Chapter 4.

3.3.4 Evaluating the Design

In line with the human-centered design (HCD) approach, evaluating the design ensures that the system aligns with user requirements and addresses user needs effectively. This activity is a pivotal stage in the HCD process, where feedback from users is gathered to assess whether the system fulfills its intended purpose. Should the design fall short of expectations, iterative improvements are made to refine the solution. Engaging actual users in the evaluation process is crucial, as they provide valuable feedback directly tied to their experiences. Figure 3.3 illustrates the usability test plan prepared for the evaluations.

Figure 3.3: Usability Testing Plan

To evaluate the design, both low-fidelity and high-fidelity prototypes were tested. The evaluation process comprised structured usability testing, including pre-test interviews, prototype interaction, post-test questionnaires, and post-test interviews. Feedback from users was collected at various stages to improve the design iteratively.

During the initial design phase, a low-fidelity prototype, created using hand-drawn sketches, was tested to explore preliminary concepts, user flow, and interface layout. Participants interacted with the sketches by tapping on drawn elements, simulating clicks and transitions. A facilitator guided each session, observing how users navigated and responded to the prototype.

Figure 3.4: One of participants interacting with the paper prototype during usability testing

Figure 3.4 show one of the participants interacting with the low-fidelity prototype during testing. Feedback was gathered from five participants who interacted with the prototype. Four out of five participants noted the absence of consistent navigation options, particularly the lack of “exit” or “back” buttons on some screens. This gap caused confusion and disrupted their navigation experience. Based on this feedback, the design was revised to include consistent navigation elements across all screens.

A high-fidelity, interactive prototype design was developed to provide a closer approximation of the final system. Before commencing usability testing, a usability test plan dashboard was prepared to outline tasks, objectives, and procedures for the sessions. The prototype allowed users to perform tasks closely aligned with real-world use cases, ensuring meaningful evaluation of usability and functionality.

System Usability Scale (SUS) Questionnaire The SUS, a ten-item Likert-scale-based instrument, was employed to gather subjective assessments of usability. Questions alternated between positively and negatively phrased statements to ensure unbiased responses. Participants rated statements such as, “I would like to use this system frequently” and “I found the system unnecessarily complex” on a five-point scale.

Testing Environment and Observations The usability testing was conducted in a controlled environment to minimize external disruptions. A table and chairs were provided for both the participant and the observer, with participants seated facing away from the observer to reduce influence. Sessions were recorded with participant consent to capture finer details, such as button-click frequencies and task completion times, which might have been missed during live observation. Feedback from these sessions highlighted key usability concerns and preferences, which were

addressed in subsequent design iterations. The iterative testing and refinement process ensured that the system evolved to better meet user needs, thereby enhancing the overall usability and user experience.

Figure 3.5: One of the participants interacting with the high-fidelity prototype, usability testing at Rwanda Heritage Hub

Iterative Design

The feedback gathered during usability testing of both low-fidelity and high-fidelity prototypes informed subsequent design iterations. Adjustments were made to improve navigation, enhance the visual hierarchy, and address user concerns about task efficiency. For example, search filters were optimized, and the playlist management interface was redesigned for better accessibility. The iterative design process ensured that the final system meets user needs and provides an intuitive, seamless experience for interacting with the digital music archive.

Figure 3.6: Iterative Testing and Improvement Process

This approach to producing design solutions demonstrates the systematic process of translating user requirements into a functional, user-centered system while maintaining a strong focus on usability and accessibility.

Chapter 4

System Analysis, Design, and Implementation

In this chapter, details the design and development process for enhancing the user experience and accessibility of the Music Cultural Heritage Digital Archives will be discussed. It will also outline the human centered design approach employed, the iterative process of developing and refining the digital archives, and the specific methodologies used to ensure that the final product meets the needs of different user groups.

4.1 Requirements Analysis

4.1.1 PACT Analysis

Designing an effective digital archive system for music cultural heritage requires a detailed understanding of how it will be used. This section uses the PACT framework (People, Activities, Context, Technology) to analyze and address user needs in a clear and structured way. By creating personas, user stories, and scenarios, the system is designed to be user-friendly, practical, and aligned with the expectations of its users[66].

Figure 4.1: PACT

A. People

The system is designed for a range of individuals, including users and collaborators. Each group plays a important role in the success of the system, and understanding their needs is essential for creating an user-friendly and effective digital archive for music heritage. Figure4.2 outlines the stakeholders as the individuals who will engage with the system

Figure 4.2: Stakeholders

Users

1. **Researchers:** Those professionals who study or use music heritage for academic purposes or to preserve cultural history. They rely on the system to access and explore music collections.
2. **Archivists:** These specialists are responsible for organizing and maintaining the archive. They ensure the content is accurately updated and categorized. In Rwanda, most archivists are employees of institutions like the National Museum and Inteko y’Umuco (Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy).
3. **Artists:** These are creative individuals who draw inspiration from traditional music and cultural heritage. The digital music archive serves as a valuable resource for them, providing access to a rich collection of traditional music that can influence their own work. By exploring the archive, artists can incorporate elements of heritage into modern compositions, preserve cultural identity through their creations, and even develop innovative art forms that bridge traditional and contemporary styles. This not only enriches their creative output but also helps keep cultural heritage alive for future generations.
4. **Lecturers, Teachers, and Instructors:** These educators use the system to teach students about history, culture, and the arts by including traditional music. The system helps them make their lessons more interesting by giving students access to music and adding interactive activities. It also helps them explain the importance of traditional music in history and culture, making the topic more engaging for students
5. **General Public Audience:** These are individuals who use the archive to explore and learn about music heritage for personal enjoyment, education, or cultural appreciation. This audience benefits from an accessible and user-friendly platform that allows them to discover traditional music, understand its historical and cultural significance, and connect with their heritage. Whether for leisure, curiosity, or learning, the archive provides a space for the public to engage with and celebrate music as an integral part of cultural identity

Institutions

The Ministry of National Unity and Civic Engagement (MINUBUMWE) plays an important role in supporting the music archive system through its institutions. It oversees the Rwanda Cultural Heritage Academy (RCHA) and the National Museum of Rwanda, both of which help preserve the country's cultural heritage[9]. RCHA shares expertise and resources to protect Rwanda's traditions, while the National Museum of Rwanda provides archival materials and cultural knowledge to strengthen the archive. Together, these collaborators ensure the archive is trustworthy, accessible, and aligned with Rwanda's cultural preservation goals.

B. Activities

The system supports various activities tailored for users, collaborators, and administrators to ensure smooth interactions with the platform.

1. For Users:

The digital music archive is designed to be open and accessible to all users, removing login barriers for exploration. Everyone can browse popular songs, top artists, frequently used instruments, and categorized genres of Rwandan traditional music, including ancient and contemporary styles.

[67]To empower lives through non-visual access to technology, the platform integrates WAI-ARIA (Web Accessibility Initiative – Accessible Rich Internet Applications) roles and attributes, ensuring screen readers can properly interpret dynamic content. We also employ semantic HTML elements, such as <header>, <nav>, <main>, and <section>, improving structure and navigation for users who rely on assistive technologies. The system is built with accessibility at its core, ensuring compliance with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)[68]. To accommodate users with low vision, a high-contrast mode enhances visibility, making it easier to distinguish text and interface elements. For individuals with cognitive disabilities, a reduced motion mode minimizes unnecessary animations and transitions, creating a more focused and less distracting experience. Users can also customize font sizes to improve readability, allowing them to adjust the text according to their comfort level. In addition, the system supports multiple languages, including English, French, and Kinyarwanda, promoting inclusivity and ensuring that users from diverse linguistic backgrounds can easily interact with the archive.

2. For Admins (Archivists):

Administrators oversee content management and improve accessibility compliance. After securely resetting their password on first login, they gain access to a dashboard with key system metrics (total songs, artist profiles, and new uploads). Administrators are responsible for organizing metadata using structured ARIA-labeled forms[67], ensuring that songs, artist profiles, and instrumental details are well-categorized for easy navigation. By implementing semantic content markup, they improve searchability and improve compatibility with screen readers, making the archive more accessible to visually impaired users. In addition, they analyze search trends to understand user behavior, refine the browsing experience, and highlight culturally significant music, ensuring that traditional Rwandan sounds remain discoverable and relevant. [68]Furthermore, by prioritizing WCAG-compliant designs and compatible assistive technology, administrators ensure that all users, regardless of ability, can access Rwanda's music heritage without barriers. This valuable information provides insight into how users interact with the archive, enabling administrators to make data-driven

decisions about future content and features. By analyzing these trends, administrators can ensure that the archive remains relevant and continues to meet the needs of its users.

C. Context

The system is designed to be flexible, mobile-responsive, and device-independent, the system ensures seamless access across desktops, tablets, and smartphones. It serves as a valuable resource for researchers, educators, museums, and music enthusiasts, contributing to the preservation and promotion of Rwanda's musical heritage.

In adherence to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)[16], the platform prioritizes user privacy and security. Strong encryption protects personal data, while user-controlled privacy settings allow individuals to manage their information with confidence. The system also upholds accessibility and data protection standards, fostering trust and inclusivity. By integrating modern UX design,[38] WAI-ARIA enhancements, and WCAG-compliant accessibility features[68], the archive guarantees an inclusive experience where everyone, including blind and visually impaired users, can explore, engage with, and celebrate Rwanda's rich musical traditions.

D. Technology

The system incorporates advanced technologies to ensure a seamless, responsive, and secure user experience.

1. **Input and Output:** Users can interact with the system using a variety of input methods, including touchscreens, keyboards and mouse commands. These options provide flexibility, allowing users to choose the most convenient or comfortable interaction mode based on their device or preferences.

The system's interface is designed to be fully responsive across different devices desktops, tablets, and smartphones ensuring a consistent, high-quality user experience. Whether accessed on a small screen or large monitor, the layout and design adapt for optimal visibility and usability.

2. Other technological Features

Performance and Scalability: The system is built to handle high traffic, offering fast loading times and supporting up to 1,000 concurrent users without performance degradation. This ensures a smooth experience even during peak usage.

Accessibility: The system complies with WCAG 2.1 guidelines, ensuring it is usable for people with disabilities. The use of Accessible Rich Internet Applications (ARIA) standards improves accessibility, enabling users with different needs to navigate and interact with the archive effectively[67].

Security and Compliance: Data is encrypted to ensure privacy and security, and the system adheres to international data protection regulations such as GDPR. This compliance guarantees that users' personal information is safeguarded[16].

Maintenance: The system is designed with modular updates in mind, ensuring easy updates and improvements without service interruptions. It also guarantees 99.9% uptime, ensuring that users can rely on the system for continuous access, with regular backups to protect data integrity.

This combination of input flexibility, responsive design, performance optimization, accessibility features, security, and efficient maintenance ensures that the system meets the diverse needs of its users while maintaining a high standard of performance and protection

4.1.2 User Stories, Personas, and User Scenarios

Following the PACT analysis (People, Activities, Context, Technology)[66], a clear understanding of the main factors influencing the system was established. This analysis provided valuable understanding into the different needs, roles, and interactions of users with the digital music archive. Based on this foundation, user stories, personas, and user scenarios were created to represent the goals, behaviors, and expectations of different user groups. These elements played a key role in shaping a user-centered design, ensuring the system meets the specific needs of educators, researchers, archivists, artists, and the general public. By addressing these factors thoroughly, the archive was designed to provide an efficient, and culturally meaningful experience.

User Stories

To design a user-focused digital music archive, user stories were developed to capture the needs, goals, and expectations of different users. These stories provide clear insights into how various stakeholders engage with the system and highlight the specific outcomes they aim to achieve. Each user story follows a simple structure to ensure clarity and alignment with system features: “As a [type of user], I want to [an action] so that [a benefit/result].”

The following are user stories:

1. As an educator, I want to search for traditional songs based on instruments and genres so that I can use them as teaching materials to educate students about Rwandan cultural heritage.
Researcher
2. As a researcher, I want to explore the archive by combining search criteria like artist and genre so that I can analyze patterns and trends in Rwandan music for academic purposes.
3. As a music lover, I want to browse and stream popular tracks on the platform so that I can enjoy and appreciate Rwandan music in an easy and engaging way.
4. As an admin, I want to upload and categorize new tracks with metadata, such as title and genre, so that the archive stays organized and accessible to all users.
5. As an artist, I want to discover traditional songs in the archive so that I can incorporate them into my creative work and preserve cultural influences in my music.
6. As a representative of a cultural institution, I want to contribute archival materials and provide feedback on the archive’s structure so that it aligns with national cultural preservation goals.
7. As a guest user, I want to freely explore the music archive at any time, browsing popular songs, top artists, traditional instruments, and categorized genres. This allows me to experience the platform’s accessibility features, seamless navigation, and rich cultural content without any restrictions, ensuring easy access to Rwanda’s musical heritage.

Personas

Personas are fictional characters created to represent different types of users. They help guide the design process by providing a clear picture of who the system is for. The personas below were designed using Figma and are included as Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.5. More detailed Personas can be found in Appendix A.

Figure 4.4: Visually Impaired Persona

Figure 4.3: Music Enthusiast persona

Figure 4.5: Teacher Persona

These personas are essential in guiding the development of the system, ensuring it meets the needs of all the people who will interact with it. By considering what each persona needs, how they will use the system, and why their goals are important, we can create a better user experience for everyone[69].

User Scenarios

User scenarios are stories that show how different users interact with a system in real-life situations. They help designers and developers understand what users want and how they use the system. Well-made user scenarios clearly describe the steps users take to achieve their goals and highlight any problems they might face. This helps to improve the design of the system, making it easier to use and better at meeting the needs of users[70]. By using these scenarios, designers can create systems that work well for everyone, based on real user experiences. The following are user scenarios:

User Scenario 1: Educator Exploring Traditional Rwandan Music for Teaching

A secondary school educator, Marie, is preparing for a cultural studies lesson on Rwandan music. She wants to find and explore relevant traditional music from the archive to introduce her students to Rwanda’s musical heritage. Marie seeks to access this music without interrupting her own lesson preparations and without requiring additional help from the system administrators or support staff.

User Scenario 2: Artist Seeking Inspiration for a New Composition

Olivier, a local musician, is working on his new album and wants to explore traditional Rwandan music for inspiration. He wants to listen to various songs and find ones that resonate with him without having to navigate complex menus or wait for assistance from others. He hopes the sys-

tem will offer quick access to music tracks relevant to his genre and interests.

User Scenario 3: Archivist Uploading New Tracks into the System

Jean-Pierre, an archivist at the National Museum of Rwanda, needs to upload several newly recorded traditional songs to the digital archive. He is aware that the process involves uploading music files, entering metadata, and verifying the accuracy of the details. Jean-Pierre wants to ensure the process is smooth and efficient, without needing to contact administrators for help. He also hopes the system will help categorize and tag the songs correctly without manual intervention.

User Scenario 5: General User Exploring Music for Personal Enjoyment

Alice, a general user and music enthusiast, is browsing the archive to discover new tracks. She wants to explore a variety of Rwandan music without being bogged down by registration processes or irrelevant content. Alice seeks an intuitive interface that allows her to stream music, discover new artists, and build a playlist seamlessly without technical interruptions.

User Scenario 4: Researcher Accessing Specific Rwandan Music for Academic Study

Dr. Grace, a researcher focusing on the evolution of Rwandan music, is preparing for a new publication. She needs to find specific songs from the 1950s to illustrate her paper. Dr. Grace wants to perform an efficient search without being overwhelmed by irrelevant tracks. She hopes the archive's search functionality will allow her to find the music she needs quickly and without errors.

User Scenario 6: Guest User Browsing and Exploring Music Tracks

Julien, a guest user who is new to Rwandan music, is visiting the archive to get a sense of its offerings. He wants to listen to a few songs and read track descriptions before deciding whether to sign up for a full account. Julien is not looking to interact with advanced features but just wants to explore the archive's content casually, hoping for an easy way to enjoy a preview of what the system has to offer.

User Scenario 7: Admin Checking System Analytics and Usage Patterns

Samuel, an admin overseeing the digital archive, wants to check the platform's usage statistics, including popular songs, user demographics, and engagement trends. He needs the data to make informed decisions about content promotion and platform improvement. Samuel hopes to access the analytics dashboard quickly and view clear reports without having to request detailed reports or assistance from other team members.

User Scenario 8: A Visually Impaired User Accessing the Archive

Ntwali Rugamba, a retired teacher and lifelong fan of traditional Rwandan music, accesses the archive using assistive technologies. With screen reader support, keyboard navigation, high-contrast mode, adjustable fonts, and multilingual options, he seamlessly explores songs, artist backgrounds, and track descriptions. The reduced motion setting enhances his browsing experience, ensuring a distraction-free environment. Through these accessibility features, Ntwali easily reconnects with his musical heritage, demonstrating the archive's commitment to inclusivity for visually impaired users.

4.1.3 Requirements Specification

This section outlines the functional and non-functional requirements identified for the system. These requirements have been carefully specified and documented after thoroughly analyzing the system's context and stakeholder needs. They are presented in the Volere template format for clarity and consistency, there are 11 total Volere shell cards, 6 for functional requirements and 5 for non function requirements[65].

Requirement No	Requirement Type	Description
REQ-001	Functional Requirement	Admins must be able to log in with credentials. Users can browse as guests with limited access.
REQ-002	Functional Requirement	Admins can view total numbers of songs, artists, and categories on the dashboard, and manage tracks.
REQ-003	Functional Requirement	Users can explore the music archive, view top artists, and search for songs, genres, and instruments.
REQ-004	Functional Requirement	Admins can upload/edit track metadata, update artist profiles, and categorize songs.
REQ-005	Functional Requirement	Users must be able to stream or preview tracks on the platform.
REQ-007	Non-Functional Requirement	The system must load the landing page within 3 seconds and return search results within 2 seconds for 10,000 entries.
REQ-008	Non-Functional Requirement	User passwords must be encrypted, and the platform must comply with GDPR.
REQ-009	Non-Functional Requirement	The platform must support English, French, and Kinyarwanda.
REQ-010	Non-Functional Requirement	Users should be able to switch between light and dark themes.
REQ-011	Non-Functional Requirement	The platform must be fully responsive across desktops, tablets, and mobile devices.

Table 4.1: Summary of System Requirements

Functional Requirements

The following are two functional requirements presented as Volere shell cards, which outline the essential features and functionalities that the system must support. These requirements are key to ensuring that the system meets user needs effectively and efficiently. Functional Requirement REQ-003 focuses on user access to the music archive, allowing them to explore the content, search for artists, and view genres, songs, and instruments. On the other hand, Functional Requirement REQ-004 outlines the capabilities for administrators to upload and manage metadata for tracks, update artist profiles, and categorize songs. These functionalities ensure that both users and administrators can interact with the system seamlessly. The Volere shell cards provide a clear structure for defining these requirements, making it easier to assess system performance and ensure all user needs are met. Additional requirements can be found in Appendix B for further reference, offering a more comprehensive overview of the system’s functional specifications.

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-003
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users exploring the music archive; Users searching for artists, genres, instruments, and songs
<i>Description:</i>	Users should be able to access the landing page, view top artists, and explore the music archive. Users can also search for specific artists, genres, and songs and instruments.
<i>Rationale:</i>	A well-organized music archive encourages engagement, allowing users to easily discover content.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder, User Research
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	The landing page should display top artists, genres, and songs. Search functionality must be available.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (engaging content discovery)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Low (search functionality not working well)

Figure 4.6: Functional Requirement REQ-003

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-004
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Admin uploading and editing track metadata; Admin updating artist profiles and categorizing songs
<i>Description:</i>	Admins should be able to upload and manage track metadata, update artist profiles, and categorize songs by instruments and genres.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Metadata management is crucial for proper organization and searchability within the music archive.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Admins can manage metadata for tracks and artists. Songs can be categorized by genre and instrument.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (streamlined content management)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Low (difficulty in metadata entry)

Figure 4.7: Functional Requirement REQ-004

Non-Functional Requirements

The following are two Non-Functional Requirements presented as Volere shell cards, which focus on the quality attributes, performance, and constraints of the system. These requirements are designed to ensure that the system operates effectively, securely, and efficiently under various con-

ditions. Non-Functional Requirement 1 emphasizes the importance of fast performance, specifying that the system must load the landing page within three seconds and return search results in under two seconds for up to 10,000 entries. Non-Functional Requirement 2 focuses on data security, requiring that user passwords be stored securely with encryption and that the platform must comply with GDPR regulations to protect user privacy. These non-functional requirements address critical factors such as performance, security, and usability, ensuring that the system meets high standards. The Volere shell cards provide a structured approach to documenting these requirements, making it easier to ensure they are met during system development. Additional non-functional requirements are provided in Appendix B for further reference, offering more detailed guidance on the system’s quality attributes.

<i>Requirement No:</i>	<i>REQ-010</i>
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Non-Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users toggling between light and dark themes
<i>Description:</i>	Users should be able to switch between light and dark themes.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Personalization improves the user experience by catering to different visual preferences.
<i>Source:</i>	User research, accessibility standards
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Toggle option available for dark and light themes.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (customizable experience)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Low (theme inconsistencies)

Figure 4.8: Non Functional Requirement 1

<i>Requirement No:</i>	<i>REQ-011</i>
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Non-Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users accessing the platform across devices
<i>Description:</i>	The platform must be fully responsive and optimized for desktops, tablets, and mobile devices.
<i>Rationale:</i>	A responsive design ensures that users have a seamless experience regardless of their device.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder, User Research
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Platform should adapt to different screen sizes. No functionality should break when switching devices.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (responsive design)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Medium (layout issues on smaller devices)

Figure 4.9: Non Functional Requirement 2

4.1.4 Conceptual Model and Task Analysis

To create a design solution that aligns with the user requirements identified during the early stages of the project, a combination of design and analysis techniques was employed. This section outlines how the solution for the music archive interface was developed, incorporating techniques such as a conceptual model, hierarchical task analysis (HTA), and both low-fidelity and high-fidelity prototyping.

Conceptual Model

Before development began, a conceptual model was created to demonstrate how the music archive system would function and how users, such as archivists and music enthusiasts, would interact with it. The conceptual model provides a high-level visualization of how tasks are performed and how the system responds to user actions. This model ensured that all identified user requirements were systematically addressed, offering a blueprint for the system’s architecture and functionality.

The model categorizes tasks into User Actions (e.g., search for music, Discover music archive) and System Actions (e.g., display search results, recommend similar tracks). It highlights the interaction flow between users and the system, ensuring that the interface supports essential functionalities like exploring the archive, managing collections, and accessing digital heritage materials.

Figure 4.10: Conceptual Model of the Music Archive System

Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA)

To further analyze user interaction with the system, a Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA) was conducted. The HTA breaks down complex tasks into smaller, manageable subtasks, enabling a clear understanding of how users will achieve their objectives within the system. For example, the task of “Search for a Music Track” is divided into subtasks like inputting a keyword, filtering results by genre, and playing a preview.

This method helped refine the workflow and user interface design by ensuring that the system supports efficient task completion while minimizing cognitive load.

Figure 4.11: Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA)

4.2 System Design

4.2.1 Current analog system of Music cultural heritage archive

There are many obstacles in the way of managing and maintaining analogue music archives in the context of cultural heritage. Because many institutions lack the facilities essential to properly store and maintain sensitive analogue recordings, poor storage facilities due to environmental conditions frequently fall short of optimal levels, exposing records to the danger of loss from things like dust and light exposure, uncontrolled humidity, and temperature changes. These difficulties make the setting for the preservation of analogue music archives complicated and even depressing. The preservation of priceless cultural heritage materials necessitates concerted efforts to upgrade infrastructure, hire qualified workers, strengthen legislative backing, and adapt right methodology and human-centred design approach.

4.3 Prototyping and User Involvement

4.3.1 Wireframes and Low Fidelity Prototyping

The design process began with the development of low-fidelity prototypes, which consisted of simple wireframes to visualize the basic layout, user interface elements, and navigation flow. These paper prototypes were created to test the structure of the interface and task flow without focusing on visual aesthetics. Early feedback from users was used to iteratively refine these wireframes before moving to more detailed designs.

Figure 4.12: Low-Fidelity Prototype: Home Page

Figure 4.13: Low-Fidelity Prototype: Discover Music Page

4.3.2 High Fidelity Prototyping

After refining the low-fidelity prototypes, high-fidelity prototypes were developed to provide a realistic, interactive representation of the system. These prototypes featured detailed visual designs, interactive elements, and functional workflows. Figma was used to create an engaging and immersive experience, allowing users to navigate through the interface and perform key tasks like browsing the music archive, managing playlists, and accessing metadata.

The high-fidelity prototypes were interactive, enabling users to experience the system as if it were fully functional. For instance, users could click buttons to search for tracks, view album details, or add songs to playlists. These prototypes allowed for usability testing, where participants provided feedback on the design, functionality, and overall user experience.

Figure 4.14: High-Fidelity Prototype – Interactive Home Page

4.4 System Development and Implementation

The development of the system followed an Agile methodology, which emphasizes iterative progress, collaboration, and flexibility. Agile was chosen to accommodate the evolving requirements and frequent feedback from stakeholders. Each sprint focused on delivering incremental features that could be reviewed and refined.

4.4.1 System Architecture

The system architecture is designed to provide a seamless, scalable, and efficient platform for managing the digital cultural heritage archive. The client-side application is built using Vue.js, a modern JavaScript framework known for its simplicity and flexibility, enabling the creation of responsive and dynamic user interfaces. Vue.js components were employed to modularize the design, promoting reusability and maintainability, while the Vue Router ensures smooth naviga-

tion between different views. Axios facilitates efficient HTTP communication between the client and server. This architecture is illustrated in Figure 4.15, providing an overview of the system's components and their integration.

Figure 4.15: System Architecture

On the server side, the application uses the power of Node.js and Nest.js. Node.js was chosen for its asynchronous and non-blocking nature, ensuring optimal performance under high traffic conditions. Nest.js, a progressive framework built on Node.js, was integrated to provide a structured and scalable approach to building the back-end, particularly for handling RESTful APIs. This combination supports a clean, modular design, making it easier to implement and maintain server-side logic. MongoDB, a NoSQL database, is used for data storage, offering flexibility for managing unstructured and semi-structured data. Additionally, an Object Data Modeling (ODM) tool simplifies database interactions, ensuring schema-based consistency and efficient data handling.

This architecture was selected to address the system's specific requirements, providing flexibility for future enhancements, high performance for real-time user interactions, and a maintainable structure for developers. With inspiration drawn from resources like Grokonez tutorials, the integration of Vue.js, Nest.js, and MongoDB forms a robust foundation. These technologies work together to deliver an intuitive and efficient experience for users while ensuring the system remains adaptable to evolving needs.

4.4.2 Multi-Layered Architecture

In the system's multi-layered architecture, the client layer, business logic layer, and database layer work together to ensure smooth operation and effective data flow. The client layer, built with Vue.js, is responsible for delivering a dynamic and interactive user interface. This layer communicates with the business logic layer via HTTP requests, ensuring that users can access and interact with data seamlessly across desktop and mobile devices. The decision to use Vue.js was driven by its reactivity, ease of integration, and ability to create a smooth, responsive front-end experience. As shown in Figure 4.16, this design ensures optimal user interaction with minimal latency.

Figure 4.16: Multi-Layered Architecture

The business logic layer, supported by Node.js and Express, handles the application's core functionality, processing requests and providing necessary responses. This layer acts as an intermediary, interpreting user inputs and making appropriate data requests to the database layer. The choice of Node.js was made for its non-blocking, event-driven architecture, which allows for efficient handling of multiple simultaneous requests. Express further enhances this by providing a lightweight framework to manage routing, authentication, and data validation. This design choice was specifically made for the thesis to handle high concurrency and reduce processing time, ensuring that the system is both scalable and responsive.

The database layer, represented by MongoDB, stores and manages the data. As a NoSQL database, MongoDB allows for flexible schema design, which is essential for handling the diverse types of data in a music archive. Its scalability ensures the system can grow with the increasing volume of data, while its performance capabilities provide fast data retrieval for a seamless user experience. The architecture has been chosen for this thesis because of its flexibility, scalability, and performance, making it an ideal solution for the demands of a digital cultural heritage archive. The combination of these layers ensures that the system is efficient, maintainable, and capable of handling user demands effectively.

4.4.3 Other Tools and Technologies

WebStorm (Integrated Development Environment):

WebStorm, a powerful and intelligent IDE developed by JetBrains, was instrumental in the development of both the backend and frontend for the digital archive project. Its features, such as auto-completion, debugging, and version control integration, played a key role in improving productivity during development.

Figure 4.17: Back-end code-base structure

Figure 4.18: Front-end code-base structure

Figures 4.17 and 4.17 showcase the source code of the backend and frontend, respectively, illustrating how the codebase is structured. VS Code facilitated quick error detection and efficient workflow management, helping ensure the smooth development of the archive system.

Git & GitHub

Git and GitHub played a critical role in managing and tracking the source code for the thesis project. Version control with Git allowed changes to be tracked over time, ensuring that the archive system's development remained organized. GitHub provided a platform to store and collaborate on the project's code. The back-end and front-end code was stored in repository. This setup facilitated seamless collaboration, efficient version management, and the ability to quickly revert to previous versions, which was key in ensuring the high quality and reliability of the archive system.

Figure 4.19: GitHub Repository code-base

OpenAPI and Swagger

OpenAPI specifications and Swagger tools was used to test and debug backend APIs. Swagger's interactive documentation allowed for the simulation of requests and responses, ensuring all API endpoints worked as expected. This approach facilitated early testing, improved efficiency in backend development, and enhanced the overall quality of the system. By leveraging OpenAPI and Swagger, the project benefited from structured API testing and documentation, aligning with agile development methodologies and ensuring the stability and scalability of the digital system.

Figure 4.20: Swagger simplifies API testing

4.4.4 Integration and Testing

Integration

The integration process involved connecting the frontend, backend, and database components into a cohesive system. API endpoints developed using NestJS were consumed by the Vue.js frontend. MongoDB served as the database, with Prisma managing data flow between the application layers.

Figure 4.21: MongoDB Atlas was chosen for its robust scalability and reliability

Testing Strategies: Ensuring a Seamless and Accessible Experience

When i set out to build the Rwandan Music Cultural Heritage Archive, I knew one thing for sure: Traditional music was at risk of being forgotten and technology had the potential to be a bridge or

a barrier. Many existing digital archives were difficult to use; see example figure 2.3, especially for visually impaired users and those unfamiliar with complex interfaces. Navigation was confusing, search functions were frustratingly ineffective, and accessibility was often an afterthought. We needed to do things differently. The only way to guarantee a truly inclusive experience was to thoroughly test all aspects of the system, ensuring that anyone, regardless of ability, could explore and appreciate Rwanda's rich musical heritage.

Unit Testing:

Before focusing on the user experience, we had to ensure that the foundation of our system was solid. Unit testing played a crucial role in verifying that each component functioned as expected. On the backend, we tested API endpoints to confirm that data retrieval and streaming worked smoothly, ensuring users could browse, search, and play music without delays. The database was also tested to handle metadata efficiently, allowing seamless organization of songs by artist, instrument, and genre, as you can see on this figure 4.21. In the front-end, we focus on the interactive elements, buttons, search filters, and media players. It was essential that clicking a song title led to an instant playback experience,

Figure 4.22: Show search that filtering by instruments like the inanga or umuduri provided accurate results.

And that users could switch between languages effortlessly. Through rigorous unit testing, we identified and fixed bugs before they could affect real users, making the system more stable and reliable.

System Testing

Once the individual parts were working well, we had to ensure they functioned seamlessly together. System testing was our way of walking in the users' shoes, verifying that the entire journey from landing on the homepage to playing a song was smooth and intuitive.

We simulated different scenarios: What happens when a user searches for a song but misspells the name? Does streaming still work properly on mobile devices? These real-world tests revealed flaws that would have frustrated users. By refining the search algorithm, optimizing the site for mobile responsiveness, and ensuring music playback remained uninterrupted, we created a plat-

form that felt natural and easy to use.

User Testing

Building a digital archive system wasn't just about storing music, It was about making it accessible to everyone, including those who rely on assistive technologies. This was where user testing became our most valuable tool. We invited real users, including visually impaired individuals and older adults unfamiliar with digital interfaces, to explore the platform. Their feedback was eye-opening.

One of our test participants, a retired teacher who had lost his sight, shared his frustration with other online archives. "I cannot tell where to click and the screen reader keeps getting stuck," he said. We wanted to change that. To enhance accessibility for visually impaired users, we incorporated semantic HTML elements and added ARIA labels to our platform's interactive components. As shown in the image below, these enhancements facilitate navigation for users who rely on screen readers like Non Visual Desktop Access (NVDA)[71]. Using ARIA[67] labels, we ensured that assistive technologies could provide clear and meaningful descriptions of each element, such as buttons and headings, allowing users to understand their functions and interact with the platform effectively. This approach significantly improves the user experience for visually impaired users, enabling them to navigate the platform with ease and confidence[72].


```
<div class="relative z-50">
  <h1
    id="Landing-page"
    class="text-white text-4xl font-extrabold mb-4"
    tabindex="0"
  >
    Rwanda Traditional Music Heritage
  </h1>
  <p
    class="text-gray-100 text-lg mb-8"
    tabindex="0"
  >
    {{ $t('dictionary.intro_description') }}
  </p>
  <router-link
    to="/discover"
    class="bg-gray-100 text-black px-6 py-3 hover:bg-gray-600 transition font-medium uppercase"
    aria-label="Explore Music Archive"
  >
    {{ $t('dictionary.explore_archive') }}
  </router-link>
</div>
</div>
</aside>
```

Figure 4.23: ARIA labels improve accessibility by providing descriptions for screen readers, helping visually impaired users navigate.

Now, when Ntwali navigated through the archive, he could easily locate songs, switch languages, and adjust playback settings without guessing.

We also carried out user tests during the Indirimbo Zicurangisho Gakondo exhibition in 2023 [7], a showcase of Rwanda's traditional music and dance. Visitors interacted with our digital archive via touchscreens and mobile devices, revealing important insights. Some users struggled to find specific songs because the menu labels were unclear, so we refined the interface using WAVE to ensure that headings and landmarks were structured for screen readers. In addition, participants with low vision pointed out issues with color contrast and missing alt text for images. We addressed these problems using Lighthouse by adding a high-contrast mode and descriptive labels for the images. Furthermore, interactive elements such as audio previews and search filters

required ARIA states to announce updates to screen readers. We used Axe DevTools to identify unlabeled buttons, which we then fixed to ensure keyboard accessibility for all users. We also had the opportunity to showcase our digital archive solution at an exhibition, where we presented the platform as a means of preserving traditional music and cultural heritage. This exhibition provided a valuable platform to demonstrate how our digital archive can help to protect and promote cultural traditions for future generations.

Figure 4.24: We presented the solution of a digital archive platform in exhibition.

4.4.5 Deployment Strategy

Hosting and Deployment Environments: The application was deployed on a cloud platform using Render, which provided high availability and scalability. Render's serverless architecture allowed for automatic scaling, ensuring that the system could adapt to changing demands without manual intervention. This deployment strategy enabled efficient resource allocation and minimized downtime, aligning with best practices for cloud scalability and reliability.

To ensure security, the deployment environment was designed with robust security measures. Data encryption was implemented to protect sensitive information both in transit and at rest, using industry-standard protocols like TLS for data transmission and AES-256 for storage[45]. Identity and Access Management (IAM) policies were established to control access to cloud resources, with role-based access control (RBAC) and multi-factor authentication (MFA) to limit access to authorized users only.

Monitoring and Maintenance: A comprehensive monitoring system was set up to track system performance and detect potential security issues in real-time[47]. Cloud Security Posture Management (CSPM) tools were used to monitor for misconfigurations and vulnerabilities, ensuring compliance with security standards and industry regulations. Regular security assessments and penetration testing were conducted to identify and address vulnerabilities proactively.

Maintenance and Update Plans: A maintenance schedule was established to ensure regular updates, including security patches, feature enhancements, and bug fixes. Automated tasks, such as

scaling and backup, were implemented to minimize manual intervention and reduce the risk of human error. Continuous monitoring and threat detection tools were used to identify potential issues early, ensuring timely interventions to maintain system stability and security.

Figure 4.25: Used Render as Hoster cloud platform

4.5 Security and Privacy Considerations

All user data, including passwords, were securely encrypted using industry-standard algorithms. JWT[73] was implemented for secure user authentication and session management[46] and also the system was designed to comply with privacy regulations such as GDPR, ensuring the protection of user data[16]. Measures were taken to handle data retention, user consent, and access controls appropriately.

MongoDB's robust security features, such as access control and data encryption, were leveraged to protect stored data. Regular backups ensured data reliability and disaster recovery. The Rwanda Music Archive System employs a robust security architecture built on NestJS, integrating encryption, authentication, and compliance measures to protect user data while ensuring a seamless experience.

4.5.1 Authentication & Authorization Implementation

JWT Authentication Flow

1. **User Login:** Clients authenticate via `/auth/login` with a username/password.
2. **Token Issuance:** On successful login, the server returns a JWT (valid for 15 minutes) and a refresh token.

```

1 // auth/auth.service.ts
2 @Injectable()
3 export class AuthService {
4   constructor(
5     private usersService: UsersService,
6     private jwtService: JwtService,
7   ) {}

```

```

8  async login(@Body() loginDto: LoginDto): Promise<{ access_token: string
    }> {
9      const user = await this.userService.findOneByEmail(loginDto.email);
10
11     if (
12         !(await this.hashService.comparePassword(
13             loginDto.password,
14             user.password,
15         ))
16     ) {
17         throw new UnauthorizedException();
18     }
19     const payload = { sub: user.id, username: user.email };
20
21     return {
22         access_token: await this.jwtService.signAsync(payload),
23     };
24 }
25
26 async generateResetToken(email: string) {
27     const existingUser = await this.userService.findOneByEmail(email);
28
29     if (!existingUser) throw new NotFoundException('User not found');
30
31     const token = this.jwtService.sign(
32         { email },
33         { secret: jwtConstants.resetSecret, expiresIn: '15m' },
34     );
35
36     await this.db.user.update({
37         where: { email },
38         data: { resetToken: token },
39     });
40
41     await this.emailService.sendPasswordReset(email, token);
42
43     return { message: 'Password reset email sent' };
44 }
45
46 async resetPassword(dto: PasswordResetDto) {
47     try {
48         const payload = this.jwtService.verify(dto.token, {
49             secret: jwtConstants.resetSecret,
50         });
51
52         const user = await this.db.user.findUnique({
53             where: { email: payload.email },
54         });
55
56         if (!user || user.resetToken !== dto.token)
57             throw new BadRequestException('Invalid or expired token');
58
59         const hashedPassword = await this.hashService.hashPassword(
60             dto.newPassword,
61         );
62
63         await this.db.user.update({
64             where: { email: payload.email },
65             data: { password: hashedPassword, resetToken: null },
66         });
67

```

```

68     return { message: 'Password reset successful' };
69   } catch (error) {
70     console.error(error);
71     throw new BadRequestException('Invalid or expired token');
72   }
73 }
74 }

```

Listing 4.1: auth.services.ts

```

1     // music/music.controller.ts
2 @Controller('music')
3 export class MusicController {
4   @Get('archives')
5   @UseGuards(JwtAuthGuard)
6   getArchives() {
7     return 'Protected music archive data';
8   }
9 }

```

Listing 4.2: music.controller.ts

Security Enhancements

The system employs strong data protection mechanisms, including hashing user passwords with bcrypt and encrypting data at rest using AES-256[46]. All API communications are secured with TLS 1.3. Session management utilizes short-lived JWTs (15 mins) paired with refresh tokens (7 days), along with a token revocation mechanism for compromised accounts.

User Experience Considerations Authentication is streamlined with clear error messages for invalid credentials and automated session renewal via refresh tokens. The system also incorporates human-centered design elements, such as rate limiting with informative headers and token expiration warnings. Regular audits and automated security scans using tools like Snyk/SonarQube ensure compliance with Rwanda’s Data Protection Law and GDPR[16].

4.5.2 Challenges and Solutions

During the development of our digital archive, we encountered several challenges. Integrating diverse technologies such as Vue.js, NestJS, and MongoDB required addressing compatibility issues, which we resolved through extensive testing and utilizing well-documented libraries. Additionally, limited time posed challenges in meeting deadlines, but we adapted by using Agile methodology. This approach allowed us to prioritize and iteratively develop critical features, ensuring they were delivered on time. Agile enabled us to break down the project into manageable sprints, gather regular feedback, and make adjustments as needed. This flexibility was crucial in responding to evolving requirements and ensuring that our platform met user needs effectively. To improve efficiency, we utilized version control tools like Git and GitHub, and also employed Snyk for security monitoring and Netlify for automated deployment processes. This combination of tools and methodologies helped us navigate technical limitations and resource constraints effectively.

Figure 4.26: Using Snyk for security monitoring

4.6 User Interfaces of New System

Welcome to our digital archive, where the vibrant sounds of Rwanda come alive. On our landing page, you're greeted by a stunning background image of a man playing the inanga, a traditional Rwandan stringed instrument symbolizing Rwanda's rich musical heritage. **"Explore Archive"** button invites you to discover traditional songs like ibihozo and kuvugira inka, while animations guide you through the platform. To ensure inclusivity, we've included an accessibility **button** that helps users with vision impairments customize their experience. This feature allows them to adjust font size, switch to high-contrast mode, and remove animations, ensuring everyone can enjoy Rwanda's rich musical heritage in a way that suits their needs.

Figure 4.27: Welcome page

4.6.1 Explore Archive

When you click "Explore Archive," you're taken to the Discover page, where you can use a powerful search bar to find specific songs, instruments, artists, or song categories. You can also browse popular artists, explore popular songs, play music directly, and read artist biographies. This feature-rich page provides a seamless and personalized music exploration experience.

Figure 4.28: Exploring cultural heritage through digital music archive

4.6.2 Discover Artist

Navigate to Discover artist, play their music, and read their biographies, gaining a deeper understanding of their lives and work.

Figure 4.29: Play songs of the artist’s most popular songs, with options to listen to preview bio

Accessibility Button

Accessibility button plays a crucial role in making your digital archive platform more inclusive and user-friendly for visually impaired individuals, aligning with broader accessibility standards and enhancing the overall user experience.

Figure 4.30: Implemented accessible buttons throughout the platform.

Admin Dashboard

Once authenticated, administrators can access the admin panel to manage the digital music archive effectively. They can upload new songs, view and manage the overall collection of songs, and oversee the list of featured artists.

Figure 4.31: Authenticated user Dashboard

Adding Songs

When an administrator uploads a song to the digital archive, they can include essential metadata such as the artist's name, the instruments used, and other relevant details. This metadata is crucial for organizing and searching the archive efficiently.

ADMIN PANEL

- Dashboard
- Tracks

View List of Tracks **Add New a Track**

Track Info
Audio file and title are required.

Artist Info
At least one artist must be added.

Other Metadata
Genre must be selected.

Summary & Submit

Step 1: Track Info

Song Title

Select song style...

Select song tunes...

Choose File | No file chosen

dd/mm/yyyy

Language

Enter lyrics

Previous Next

A11y

Nono Agent
Administrator
Log Out

Figure 4.32: Adding songs into system

4.7 Project source code

The following snapshot provides a sample of the backend code, illustrating its structure and functionality. It demonstrates key implementations, such as data processing, API handling, and logic execution, which contribute to the overall operation of the system. The full source code file can be found in the GitHub repository [2]

```

1 import { Body, Controller, Post } from '@nestjs/common';
2 import { AuthService } from '../auth.service';
3 import { RegisterDto } from '../dto/register.dto';
4 import { LoginDto } from '../dto/login.dto';
5 import { Public } from '../decorators/auth.decorator';
6 import { ApiBearerAuth, ApiOperation, ApiResponse } from '@nestjs/swagger';
7 import { PasswordResetRequestDto } from '../dto/password-reset-request.dto';
8 import { PasswordResetDto } from '../dto/password-reset.dto';
9 import { Throttle } from '@nestjs/throttler';
10 // import { JwtAuthGuard } from '../guard/jwt-auth.guard';
11
12 @ApiBearerAuth()
13 @Controller('auth')
14 export class AuthController {
15   constructor(private readonly authService: AuthService) {}
16
17   // @UseGuards(JwtAuthGuard)
18   @Post('register')
19   register(@Body() registerDto: RegisterDto) {
20     return this.authService.register(registerDto);
21   }
22
23   // @Throttle({ default: { limit: 3, ttl: 60000 } })
24   @Public()
25   @Post('login')
26   async signIn(@Body() signInDto: LoginDto) {
27     return await this.authService.login(signInDto);
28   }

```

```

29
30 @Public()
31 @Post('request-password-reset')
32 @ApiOperation({ summary: 'Request a password reset link' })
33 @ApiResponse({ status: 200, description: 'Password reset email sent' })
34 async requestPasswordReset(@Body() dto: PasswordResetRequestDto) {
35     return this.authService.generateResetToken(dto.email);
36 }
37
38 @Public()
39 @Post('reset-password')
40 @ApiOperation({ summary: 'Reset the user password' })
41 @ApiResponse({ status: 200, description: 'Password successfully reset' })
42 async resetPassword(@Body() dto: PasswordResetDto) {
43     return this.authService.resetPassword(dto);
44 }
45 }

```

Listing 4.3: Login Controller

The snapshot below presents an example of the frontend code, showcasing its organization and key components. It highlights essential features such as user interface rendering, state management, and event handling, which play a crucial role in the system's overall functionality.

The complete source code is available in the GitHub repository [2].

```

1 <template>
2   <div class="bg-gray-200 w-full min-h-screen flex items-center justify-center
3     ">
4     <div class="w-full py-8">
5       <div class="bg-white w-5/6 md:w-3/4 lg:w-2/3 xl:w-[500px] 2xl:w-[550px]
6         mt-8 mx-auto px-16 py-8 rounded-lg shadow-2xl">
7         <div class="flex">
8           <div class="flex items-center justify-center mb-4 gap-4">
9             
11             <h1 class="text-3xl font-bold text-[#00A4E4] tracking-wider">RHCA
12             </h1>
13           </div>
14           <div class="ml-auto mt-2">
15             <a href="/welcome" aria-label="Go to Homepage">
16               <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" width="24" height="24"
17                 viewBox="0 0 24 24"><path fill="none" stroke="currentColor"
18                   stroke-linecap="round" stroke-linejoin="round" stroke-width=
19                     "2" d="M18 6L6 18M6 6l12 12"/></svg>
20             </a>
21           </div>
22         </div>
23         <div>
24           </div>
25         </div>
26       </div>
27       <div>
28         </div>
29     </div>
30   </div>
31   <div class="flex flex-row gap-2">
32     <div>
33       <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" width="24" height="24"
34         viewBox="0 0 24 24"><g fill="none" stroke="currentColor"
35           stroke-linecap="round" stroke-linejoin="round" stroke-width=
36             "2"><path d="M19 21v-2a4 4 0 0 0-4-4H9a4 4 0 0 0-4 4v2"/><
37             circle cx="12" cy="7" r="4"/></g></svg>
38     </div>
39     <div class="flex" >
40       <h2 class="text-start text-xl -mb-4 font-bold tracking-wide text
41         -[#00A4E4]">Injira</h2>
42     </div>

```

```

26     </div>
27 </div>
28
29 <form class="my-8 text-sm">
30   <div class="flex flex-col my-4">
31     <label for="email" class="text-gray-700">Imeri</label>
32     <input type="email" name="email" id="email" class="mt-2 p-2 border
        border-gray-300 focus:outline-none focus:ring-0 focus:border-
        gray-300 rounded text-sm text-gray-900" placeholder="Andi
        imeli">
33   </div>
34
35   <div class="flex flex-col my-4">
36     <label for="password" class="text-gray-700">Ijambo ry'ibanga</
        label>
37     <div class="relative flex items-center mt-2">
38       <input :type="visible ? 'text' : 'password'" name="password" id
        ="password" class="flex-1 p-2 pr-10 border border-gray-300
        focus:outline-none focus:ring-0 focus:border-gray-300
        rounded text-sm text-gray-900" placeholder="Andika ijambo ry
        'ibanga" type="password">
39       <button @click="visible = !visible" type="button" class="
        absolute right-2 bg-transparent flex items-center justify-
        center text-gray-700">
40         <svg v-show="!visible" class="w-5 h-5" fill="none" stroke="
        currentColor" viewBox="0 0 24 24" xmlns="http://www.w3.org
        /2000/svg"><path stroke-linecap="round" stroke-linejoin="
        round" stroke-width="2" d="M13.875 18.825A10.05 10.05 0
        0112 19c-4.478 0-8.268-2.943-9.543-7a9.97 9.97 0
        011.563-3.029m5.858 9.08a3 3 0 114.243M9.878 9.87814
        .242 4.242M9.88 9.881-3.29-3.29m7.532 7.53213.29 3.29M3 3
        13.59 3.59m0 0A9.953 9.953 0 0112 5c4.478 0 8.268 2.943
        9.543 7a10.025 10.025 0 01-4.132 5.411m0 0L21 21"></path
        ></svg>
41
42       <svg v-show="visible" class="w-5 h-5" fill="none" stroke="
        currentColor" viewBox="0 0 24 24" xmlns="http://www.w3.org
        /2000/svg" style="display: none;"><path stroke-linecap="
        round" stroke-linejoin="round" stroke-width="2" d="M15 12
        a3 3 0 11-6 0 3 3 0 016 0z"></path><path stroke-linecap="
        round" stroke-linejoin="round" stroke-width="2" d="M2.458
        12C3.732 7.943 7.523 5 12 5c4.478 0 8.268 2.943 9.542
        7-1.274 4.057-5.064 7-9.542 7-4.477 0-8.268-2.943-9.542-7z
        "></path></svg>
43     </button>
44   </div>
45 </div>
46 <div class="flex justify-between ">
47   <a href="#" class="text-[#00A4E4] hover:text-blue-400 hover:
        underline hover:-translate-y-1 duration-500 transition-all">
        Wibagiwe ijambo ry'ibanga?</a>
48   <a href="/signUp" class="text-[#00A4E4] hover:text-blue-400 hover:
        underline hover:-translate-y-1 duration-500 transition-all">
        Nta konti ufite?</a>
49 </div>
50
51 <div class="my-4 flex items-center justify-end space-x-4">
52   <button @click="goToDashboard" class="bg-[#00A4E4] hover:bg-[#00
        A4E4] rounded-lg px-8 py-2 text-gray-100 hover:shadow-xl
        hover:-translate-y-1 duration-500 transition-all">Injira</
        button>

```

```
53         </div>
54     </form>
55 </div>
56 </div>
57 </div>
58
59 </template>
60
61 <script setup>
62 import {useRouter} from "vue-router";
63 import {ref} from "vue";
64 const router = useRouter()
65 const visible = ref(false)
66
67 import inteko_image from '../.../assets/inteko_logo.png'
68
69 const goToDashboard = () => {
70     router.push('/dashboard')
71 }
72 </script>export default Login;
```

Listing 4.4: Login Component

Chapter 5

Results and Analysis

This chapter presents the findings from the usability testing, surveys, and post-test interviews conducted to evaluate the music archive system. With aim of assessing how well the system meets the needs of users in preserving Rwanda’s music cultural heritage, while also evaluating its usability and accessibility. This chapter is structured around the study’s core research questions: the effectiveness of the system in preserving musical heritage (RQ1), its usability and accessibility for a diverse user group (RQ2), and security and data integrity (RQ3).

The results are drawn from a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. The System Usability Scale (SUS)[74] and User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)[75] provide numerical data on how users perceive the system’s usability, satisfaction, and overall experience. These results highlight both the strengths and areas where the system could be improved. The post-test interviews offer additional context, with users sharing their personal experiences and concerns, which help to explain the survey results and identify specific usability challenges that were not captured in the quantitative data.

By analyzing the findings from the SUS, UEQ, the post-test interviews and related literature review, this chapter offers a comprehensive analysis of the system’s usability and accessibility. The results reveal how well the system supports user needs, and they provide valuable insights into where improvements can be made to enhance it and ensure it effectively serves as a tool for preserving Rwanda’s music heritage.

5.1 Data-Driven Assessment

5.1.1 Evaluation Using the System Usability Scale (SUS)

To assess the usability and efficiency of the digital music archive system, participants completed the System Usability Scale (SUS) after task-based testing. The SUS[64] consists of 10 questions, with odd-numbered questions reflecting positive aspects of the system and even-numbered questions focusing on potential usability challenges. Each question is rated on a five-point scale with the following meaning[76]:

The table below presents the System Usability Scale (SUS)[76] responses collected from 10 participants after task-based usability testing. These responses were gathered using the Google Survey Form[77], which can be found in Appendix C

Response	Numeric Representation
Strongly Disagree	1
Disagree	2
Neutral	3
Agree	4
Strongly Agree	5

Table 5.1: Likert Scale Responses

Questions	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
Q1: I think I would like to use this system frequently.	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	3	5	4
Q2: I found the system unnecessarily complex.	2	1	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	3
Q3: I thought the system was easy to use.	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4
Q4: I think I would need technical support to use this system.	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1
Q5: I found the various functions were well integrated.	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4
Q6: I thought there was too much inconsistency in the system.	3	2	2	2	3	1	3	3	1	2
Q7: I would imagine most people would learn to use it quickly.	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4
Q8: I found the system very cumbersome to use.	1	1	2	1	3	1	2	2	1	2
Q9: I felt very confident using the system.	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4
Q10: I needed to learn a lot before using the system.	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2

Table 5.2: SUS Responses from 10 Participants

After collecting the SUS responses, the scores were calculated using the standard formula[64], as explained in Chapter 3, to evaluate the usability, overall user experience, and for easy interpretation the table5.2 presents the SUS scores for all 10 participants converted into numeric data. Table5.3 presents the SUS scores for each participant:

Participant	SUS Score
P1	77.5
P2	92.5
P3	77.5
P4	92.5
P5	72.5
P6	95.0
P7	77.5
P8	70.0
P9	95.0
P10	77.5

Table 5.3: SUS Scores of Participants

Figure 5.1: System Usability Scale Scores Across Participants

Interpretation of SUS Results

SUS scores[74] for the music archive system ranged from 70.0 to 95.0, reflecting diverse user experiences. This variability was further explored in the post-test interviews. Participants with scores above 80 (P2, P4, P6, and P9) reported high satisfaction with the system. During the interviews, they shared that the system was easy to navigate, with well-integrated features like search and filtering contributing to their positive experience.

Participants who scored below 70 (P1, P3, P5, P7, and P10) demonstrated a satisfactory level of usability with the system but identified key areas for improvement. During interviews, they emphasized the need for better handling of some features, particularly predictive search and personalized suggestions based on past interactions. They also expressed a strong preference for quicker access to recently viewed songs and a comprehensive playback history, which they believed would enhance both usability and overall user engagement.

Implementation Analysis of Participants' Suggestions

User feedback is essential for refining the digital music archive system, ensuring it aligns with user expectations and enhances overall accessibility and engagement. During usability testing, participants who scored below 70 highlighted areas where predictive search, personalized recommendations, and playback history could be improved. These suggestions focused on enhancing content discovery, optimizing search efficiency, and providing users with more intuitive ways to access previously played songs. This section analyzes the feasibility, implementation strategies, and potential challenges of integrating these user-driven recommendations.

1. Predictive Search and Intelligent Auto Suggestions

Participants suggested that the search functionality should anticipate user intent and provide real-time suggestions based on previously searched or frequently accessed content. Since public users do not log in, traditional user profile-based recommendation models are not applicable. Instead, predictive search can be implemented using Elasticsearch[78] or Apache Solr[79], leveraging metadata indexing[80] and real-time query matching to suggest content dynamically. Machine learning techniques, such as Natural Language Processing (NLP)

models, can further enhance this feature by understanding user input patterns and search trends. However, challenges include balancing speed and accuracy, ensuring the search system remains efficient even as the archive expands.

2. Personalized Recommendations Without User Authentication

Participants expressed a need for personalized suggestions based on past interactions, even though the system does not require user logins. A feasible solution is session-based tracking, where recently searched or played songs are temporarily stored in the user's browser[81] (Local Storage or IndexedDB[80]). This allows returning users to see relevant recommendations without requiring authentication. Additionally, session cookies can be used to store user preferences temporarily during a single browsing session, enabling a dynamic recommendation system that resets when the session ends. While this approach ensures privacy compliance (GDPR-friendly)[16], a key challenge is ensuring that stored data does not become overloaded, affecting performance.

3. Quick Access to Recently Viewed and Played Songs

Participants also recommended easier access to their playback history, allowing them to resume listening to previously played tracks. Since user accounts are not available, this can be addressed by storing a limited history of played songs in browser cache or using a lightweight database such as IndexedDB[82]. This approach ensures that users can quickly revisit their previously played content without server-side storage. Additionally, integrating a "Recently Played" section on the homepage could enhance usability. However, a challenge is ensuring that the stored history does not persist indefinitely[81], which can be mitigated by implementing automatic expiration rules (e.g., storing only the last 10 played songs and clearing older entries after a fixed period).

5.1.2 Analysis of User Experience Questionnaire Responses

The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) provided a deeper understanding of the participants' perceptions of the system's attractiveness, efficiency, clarity, dependability, stimulation, and novelty[75]. Unlike the System Usability Scale (SUS), which focuses primarily on the system's overall usability and ease of use, the UEQ offered a more detailed evaluation of users' emotional responses and satisfaction with specific aspects of the system's design and functionality[83]. Each of the six dimensions was rated on a scale ranging from 1 (negative) to 5 (positive), allowing for a more nuanced understanding of how participants felt about the system's aesthetic appeal and overall user experience. The UEQ was essential to complement the SUS[64] by capturing these additional layers of user experience, providing a fuller picture of the system's performance and areas for improvement.

Questions	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
Q1: Is the design visually appealing?	4	5	4	5	3	4	5	4	4	5
Q2: Do you enjoy using this system?	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4
Q3: Were tasks completed quickly?	4	4	5	4	5	3	5	4	4	5
Q4: Does the system accomplish goals efficiently?	4	4	3	5	4	5	4	4	3	4
Q5: Do you feel confident when navigating?	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4
Q6: Is the system consistent and predictable?	4	4	3	5	4	5	4	4	4	5
Q7: Is it easy to learn to use the system?	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5
Q8: Are features clearly explained or intuitive?	5	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4
Q9: Is the system exciting to use?	4	5	3	4	5	4	5	4	4	5
Q10: Does it motivate you to explore features?	3	4	3	5	4	3	5	4	3	4
Q11: Does the system feel innovative?	4	5	4	5	3	5	5	4	4	4
Q12: Are the features creative and unique?	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	3	5

Table 5.4: Respondents' scores on the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) (1-Strongly disagree; 5-Strongly Agree)

The above table 5.5 presents the UEQ responses from 10 participants. UEQ groups questions into six dimensions to understand how users feel about the system. Attractiveness checks if the system looks good and is enjoyable to use. Perspicuity measures how easy it is to learn and understand. Efficiency looks at how well and quickly users can complete tasks. Dependability checks if the system is reliable and easy to navigate. Stimulation sees if the system is fun and keeps users interested. Novelty examines if the system is creative and has unique features. These categories help improve the music cultural heritage digital archive system by making it easier, more engaging, and more useful for users

Dimension - Question	Average Score	Standard Deviation
Attractiveness - Q1	4.3	0.48
Stimulation - Q2	4.6	0.50
Efficiency - Q3	4.2	0.40
Efficiency - Q4	4.1	0.55
Dependability - Q5	4.5	0.51
Dependability - Q6	4.3	0.48
Perspicuity - Q7	4.5	0.51
Perspicuity - Q8	4.6	0.50
Stimulation - Q9	4.2	0.40
Stimulation - Q10	3.9	0.30
Novelty - Q11	4.3	0.48
Novelty - Q12	4.2	0.40

Table 5.5: Average Scores and Standard Deviations for UEQ Questions

The average scores and standard deviations in the table represent key insights into how users perceive the usability and user experience of the music cultural heritage digital archive system.

The average score for each question reflects the overall user sentiment regarding specific aspects of the system. Higher scores indicate a more positive perception, while lower scores highlight areas needing improvement and the standard deviation measures how much users' responses vary from the average score. A low standard deviation means most users had similar opinions, while a high standard deviation indicates differing views.

Figure 5.2: Average Scores for UEQ Questions

The Figure 5.2 represents the average scores for each question from the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ), grouped by their respective dimensions. Each data point shows how participants rated various aspects of the system, such as its attractiveness, stimulation, efficiency, dependability, perspicuity, and novelty. The higher the score, the more positive the feedback, indicating strong user satisfaction in those areas. This visual summary helps highlight strengths and areas for improvement in the system's design and usability.

Findings and Interpretation of UEQ Survey Responses

The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) survey results provide valuable insights into the usability and effectiveness of the music cultural heritage digital archive system. The findings are analyzed across six key dimensions: Attractiveness, Perspicuity, Efficiency, Dependability, Stimulation, and Novelty, which help evaluate how well the system meets user needs and aligns with the study's objectives.

1. General Usability and Accessibility (Perspicuity & Efficiency)

High perspicuity scores indicate that users found the system easy to learn and navigate, suggesting that the user-centered design approach helped in making the platform intuitive. Efficiency ratings confirm that users could complete tasks without unnecessary delays, highlighting the system's effectiveness in organizing and retrieving digital music content. These findings support Objective 1 (Ensuring accessibility for diverse users) and Objective 2 (Implementing user-centered design principles), demonstrating that the system is accessible and efficient for different user groups, including researchers and the general public.

2. System Reliability and User Confidence (Dependability & Stimulation)

Moderate dependability scores suggest that while the system functions as expected, some users expressed concerns about consistency or reliability in certain interactions. Stimulation scores show that while users found the system engaging, further improvements in visual appeal and interactive features could enhance user motivation to explore the archive. These findings align with Objective 4 (Providing tools for researchers and educators) and RQ2 (Designing a usable digital archive system). Addressing dependability concerns by improving

feedback mechanisms and ensuring seamless system performance can enhance user trust and engagement.

3. Innovation and Uniqueness (Attractiveness & Novelty)

Users generally rated the system as visually appealing, confirming that the design enhances usability. However, novelty scores suggest that users did not find the system highly innovative, implying that while it is functional, it may not introduce groundbreaking features. To better address Objective 3 (Digitizing and organizing traditional Rwandan music) and RQ1 (Effective approaches for preserving music heritage), incorporating advanced search capabilities, interactive elements, or AI-driven recommendations could increase user engagement and perceived innovation.

4. Security and Data Integrity Considerations

While the survey did not explicitly measure security, dependability concerns suggest that users may require more transparency on data protection measures. This relates to Objective 5 (Protecting user information and preventing unauthorized access) and RQ3 (Essential security measures for digital archives). Enhancing security features and communicating them effectively within the system could strengthen user confidence in data integrity.

The UEQ survey results indicate that the system effectively addresses usability, efficiency, and accessibility concerns, making it a valuable tool for preserving Rwanda's music heritage. However, areas such as system reliability, engagement, and innovation require further improvements. Addressing these concerns through enhanced documentation, improved interactivity, and security transparency will help ensure that the system fully meets all research objectives and provides a sustainable solution for digital music preservation.

5.2 Qualitative Insights

5.2.1 Thematic Analysis of Post-Test Interviews

The post-test interviews provided rich qualitative data on participants' experiences with the digital music archive system. Thematic analysis was conducted to identify recurring themes and patterns in the responses. Below is a detailed analysis of the key themes that emerged from the interviews, organized by the interview questions.

Theme 1: Overall Usability and Experience

Key Findings:

Positive Feedback: Most participants found the system intuitive and well-structured. For example, P1 (UX Designer) stated, "The system is intuitive and well-structured," while P4 (General User) noted, "User-friendly, even for non-tech users." **Appreciation for Specific Features:** Participants highlighted features such as search and filtering tools (P1, P6), audio quality and metadata organization (P2), and playlist creation (P8) as particularly helpful.

Implications: The system's overall usability was well-received, with participants appreciating its intuitive design and key features. However, some users suggested improvements to enhance the experience further.

Theme 2: Ease of Use and Learnability

Key Findings:

Ease of Learning: Most participants found the system easy to learn, with P1 stating, "Very easy to learn," and P4 adding, "It was easy to pick up."

Navigation Challenges: Some participants encountered difficulties with navigation, particularly with advanced search options (P4) and filtering (P2, P3, P6, P9). For example, P2 (Traditional Music Artist) mentioned, "Had difficulty refining searches," and P9 (Archivist) noted, "Filtering was sometimes slow."

Implications: While the system was generally easy to use, improvements in navigation and filtering could enhance the user experience, especially for users with less technical expertise.

Theme 3: Accessibility and Inclusivity

Key Findings:

Accessibility Issues: Some participants identified accessibility challenges, such as small text size (P3, P7, P10) and poor color contrast (P1, P5). P1 suggested, "Improve the contrast for readability," while P7 recommended, "Option to adjust text size dynamically."

Suggestions for Improvement: Participants proposed several accessibility enhancements, including larger text options (P1), high-contrast modes (P5), and voice search functionality (P8).

Implications: The system's accessibility features need refinement to accommodate users with varying needs, such as those with visual impairments or limited technical skills.

5.2.2 Theme 4: Engagement and User Satisfaction

Key Findings:

Engagement Levels: Participants found the system engaging, particularly for research purposes (P6, P7, P9). P6 (Music Researcher) stated, "Highly engaging for researchers," while P8 (Music Enthusiast) suggested, "Could be more engaging with interactive tools."

Likelihood to Reuse: Most participants expressed a willingness to return to the system, especially if improvements were made. For example, P2 said, "I would return to explore more songs," and P9 noted, "Yes, if filtering is improved."

Implications: While the system is engaging, adding more interactive and personalized features could increase user satisfaction and long-term engagement.

Theme 5: Areas for Improvement

Key Findings:

Search and Filtering: Several participants suggested improving search and filtering options. P6 (Music Researcher) recommended, "Expand advanced search options," while P9 (Archivist) noted, "Improve search performance."

Metadata and Content: Participants emphasized the need for more detailed metadata (P3, P6, P7) and historical context (P7). P3 (Heritage Conservationist) suggested, "Expand metadata categories," and P7 (Historian) proposed, "Add a timeline visualization for historical context."

User Guidance: Some participants felt that the system could benefit from better user guidance, such as tutorials (P4) and clearer labeling (P5).

Implications: Improvements in search functionality, metadata organization, and user guidance are critical to enhancing the system's usability and appeal.

5.2.3 Theme 6: Additional Feedback and Suggestions

Key Findings:

Community Features: Several participants suggested adding community-driven features, such as user-generated playlists (P8) and expert contributions to metadata (P3).

Personalization: Participants expressed a desire for more personalized features, such as role-based customization (P10) and interactive tools (P8).

Implications: Incorporating community and personalization features could make the system more engaging and user-centric.

5.2.4 Summary of Thematic Analysis

The thematic analysis of the post-test interviews revealed several key insights:

Usability: The system was generally well-received for its intuitive design and key features, but improvements in navigation and filtering are needed.

Accessibility: While the system is accessible to most users, enhancements such as adjustable text size, high-contrast modes, and voice search could improve inclusivity.

Engagement: Participants found the system engaging, particularly for research purposes, but suggested adding more interactive and personalized features to increase satisfaction.

Areas for Improvement: Key areas for improvement include search and filtering, metadata organization, and user guidance.

Community and Personalization: Incorporating community-driven features and personalization options could enhance user engagement and long-term retention.

5.2.5 Implications for Design

Based on the thematic analysis, the following design recommendations are proposed:

Enhance Search and Filtering: Improve search functionality and filtering options to make it easier for users to find specific content.

Improve Accessibility: Add features such as adjustable text size, high-contrast modes, and voice search to accommodate users with varying needs.

Increase Engagement: Incorporate interactive and personalized features, such as user-generated playlists and role-based customization.

Expand Metadata: Provide more detailed metadata and historical context to enhance the system's value for researchers and enthusiasts.

Provide User Guidance: Add tutorials, tooltips, and clearer labeling to help users navigate the system more effectively.

This thematic analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences with the digital music archive system and offers actionable recommendations for improving its usability, accessibility, and engagement. These insights align with the study's research questions and contribute to the development of a user-friendly and inclusive digital archive for Rwandan music cultural heritage.

5.3 Addressing the Research Questions

5.3.1 Findings Related to Research Question 1

The findings contribute to understanding how the digital archive system can effectively preserve music cultural heritage. The high usability scores and positive feedback from participants suggest that the system successfully addresses the challenges of accessibility and preservation, aligning with Research Question 1.

5.3.2 Findings Related to Research Question 2

The study sheds light on the specific needs and preferences of users when interacting with a digital music archive. The preference for a user-friendly and accessible system supports Research Question 2, highlighting the importance of intuitive design and ease of use.

5.3.3 Findings Related to Research Question 3

User feedback provides actionable recommendations for refining the system's security measures. The integration of encryption and compliance with GDPR standards aligns with Research Question 3, ensuring the integrity and accessibility of music cultural heritage in a digital archive system.

5.4 Key Insights and Implications

5.4.1 Usability and Accessibility

The findings highlight that usability and accessibility are central to the effectiveness of the digital music archive system. The high scores in usability and clarity suggest that the system successfully meets the needs of diverse users, including those with disabilities.

5.4.2 Cognitive Load and Task Efficiency

The system's design minimized cognitive load, allowing users to complete tasks efficiently. Participants appreciated the streamlined navigation and intuitive interface, which reduced the effort required to interact with the archive.

5.4.3 Recommendations for Design Improvements

Based on feedback from the SUS, UEQ, and interviews, several design improvements are recommended:

Enhanced Search Functionality: Improving the search and filtering options to make it easier for users to find specific content. **Interactive Features:** Adding more interactive elements, such as user-generated playlists and social sharing options, to increase engagement. **Accessibility Enhancements:** Further improving accessibility features, such as screen reader compatibility and keyboard navigation, to ensure inclusivity for all users.

5.5 Limitations and Future Directions

5.5.1 Limitations of the Study

This study had several limitations that may affect the generalizability of its findings:

Participant Bias: Participants' familiarity with digital tools may have influenced their perceptions of the system's usability. **Data Collection Constraints:** The study relied on self-reported data from interviews and surveys, which can introduce subjective biases. **Technological Limitations:** The system's performance may vary depending on the user's device and internet connection, potentially affecting their experience.

5.5.2 Future Work

Future research should focus on:

Testing the system with a larger, more diverse user group. Exploring advanced features, such as machine learning for content personalization. Conducting longitudinal studies to assess the system's long-term usability and impact.

5.6 Conclusion

The results and analysis presented in this chapter demonstrate that the digital music archive system successfully addresses the study's research questions. The system's high usability scores, positive user feedback, and alignment with accessibility and security standards highlight its potential to preserve and enhance Rwandan music cultural heritage. Future work should focus on refining the system based on user feedback and exploring advanced features to further improve the user experience including considerations for localization as well as personalization.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Recommendation

This chapter presents the conclusion and recommendations of the study. It summarizes the findings on the design and evaluation of a digital music archive system, highlighting its strengths in preserving Rwanda's musical heritage and areas for improvement. The chapter also provides actionable recommendations to enhance usability, accessibility, and user engagement. These insights aim to refine the system for broader and more inclusive global use.

6.1 Conclusion

The study successfully designed and evaluated a digital music archive system that is usable, accessible, and engaging. The findings show that the system is effective in preserving and sharing Rwanda's music cultural heritage, but there are areas for improvement.

Most test participants found the system easy to use and navigate, with features like search, filtering, and playlist creation being particularly appreciated. However, some test participants faced challenges with advanced search options and filtering, suggesting these areas need improvement. The system was accessible to most users in a wider context of use, but some participants identified issues with small text size and poor color contrast. Improvements in accessibility, such as adjustable text size and high-contrast modes, would make the system more inclusive.

Participants found the system engaging, especially for research and exploration. Features like artifacts' metadata and historical context were highly valued. Adding more interactive and personalized features, such as user-generated playlists, could make the system even more engaging. Users also suggested improving search and filtering, expanding metadata, and providing better guidance for new users. Community-driven features, like allowing users to contribute to metadata or share playlists, could enhance the system's value and appeal.

Overall, the study demonstrates that the digital music archive system has great potential to preserve and share Rwanda's music cultural heritage. With some refinements, it can become an even more effective and inclusive tool for users worldwide.

6.2 Recommendations

Using AI and machine learning can make the system smarter and easier to use. AI can suggest songs or playlists based on what users like to listen to, making it easier to discover new music. Machine learning can also help by automatically adding song details, organizing music, and improving search results.

Adding voice search would make the system more accessible, especially for people with visual impairments or those who are not very familiar with technology. This would allow users to search for music by speaking instead of typing.

Providing better user guidance is also important. A step-by-step tutorial, tooltips, or a short demo video could help users with low digital literacy learn how to use the system easily. This would make the platform more welcoming and user-friendly.

To make the system more engaging and interactive, users should be able to create and share playlists, add song details, and leave comments or reviews. This would help build a strong community where people can connect through music.

Keeping the system updated and well-maintained is also necessary. Regular improvements and collecting feedback from users through surveys or discussions can help fix problems and make the system better over time.

By following these recommendations, the digital music archive can become a smarter, more accessible, and more enjoyable platform for sharing and preserving Rwanda's musical heritage with the world.

6.3 Future Work

To build on the findings of this study, future work could focus on several areas. Testing the system with a larger and more diverse group of users would ensure it meets the needs of different audiences. Exploring advanced technologies, such as machine learning, could personalize the user experience by adding features like recommendations based on user preferences or listening history. Conducting long-term studies to evaluate how users interact with the system over time would provide valuable insights for continuous improvement.

6.4 Final Thoughts

The digital music archive system developed in this study is a valuable tool for preserving and sharing Rwanda's music cultural heritage. The findings show that the system is usable, accessible, and engaging, but there is room for improvement. By implementing the recommendations outlined in this chapter, the system can become even more effective and inclusive, ensuring that Rwanda's rich musical traditions are preserved and celebrated for generations to come.

This study highlights the importance of human-centered design in creating digital tools for cultural heritage preservation. By listening to user feedback and continuously improving the system, we can ensure that it meets the needs of diverse users and remains a valuable resource for years to come.

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Appendix A

Personas

Figure A.1: Persona 3

Figure A.2: Persona 4

Appendix B

Additional Requirements Specification

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-001
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Admins logging in with credentials; Users browsing as guests
<i>Description:</i>	Admins must be able to log in with their credentials. Users without credentials can browse as guests with limited access.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Secure authentication is necessary to differentiate user roles and protect sensitive data. Guest access increases accessibility without compromising security.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder, Business Requirements
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Admin login and guest browsing should be available. Admin must reset their default password on first login.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (security and accessibility)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Low (complexity of password reset)

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-002
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Admins viewing total numbers of songs, artists, and categories of songs on the dashboard; Admin adding, editing tracks
<i>Description:</i>	Admins must be able to view recently added songs in the dashboard.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Providing a simple admin dashboard allows for efficient management of the music archive.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Dashboard displays statistics, and admins can manage tracks.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	Medium (easy-to-use management)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Medium (too many options can be overwhelming)

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-005
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users streaming or previewing tracks
<i>Description:</i>	Users must be able to stream or preview tracks directly on the platform.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Music playback functionality is essential for user engagement and interaction with the content.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder, User Research
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Tracks should be available for streaming or previewing.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (music enjoyment)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Medium (latency issues)

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-006
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Admin viewing analytics
<i>Description:</i>	Admins should have access to usage statistics, such as the most searched terms, popular tracks, and user demographics.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Analytics help administrators understand user behavior and improve the platform's offerings.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	The system must generate real-time usage statistics.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (insight-driven decisions)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Medium (lack of real-time updates)

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-007
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Non-Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users accessing platform efficiently
<i>Description:</i>	The system must load the landing page within 3 seconds under normal traffic, and search queries must return results within 2 seconds for up to 10,000 entries.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Fast performance is crucial to maintaining user satisfaction and engagement.
<i>Source:</i>	Project Stakeholder, User Research
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Landing page loads within 3 seconds. Search results return within 2 seconds.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (smooth experience)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	High (slow load time)

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-008
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Non-Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users ensuring data security
<i>Description:</i>	All user passwords must be stored securely using encryption, and the platform must comply with GDPR.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Security and privacy are essential to protect user information and comply with legal regulations.
<i>Source:</i>	Legal requirements, Security experts
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	User passwords are encrypted. Platform complies with GDPR data protection laws.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (privacy and security)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Low (security breaches)

<i>Requirement No:</i>	REQ-009
<i>Requirement Type:</i>	Non-Functional Requirement
<i>Use Cases:</i>	Users switching languages
<i>Description:</i>	The platform must support English, French, and Kinyarwanda languages.
<i>Rationale:</i>	Multi-language support ensures accessibility for a diverse user base.
<i>Source:</i>	User research, business requirements
<i>Fit Criterion:</i>	Language toggle available for English, French, and Kinyarwanda.
<i>Customer Satisfaction Rating:</i>	High (accessible platform)
<i>Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:</i>	Medium (translation errors)

Appendix C

System Usability Scale - Survey Form

System Usability Evaluation: Tell Us About Your Experience!

Evaluate how easy and efficient the system is to use. Your feedback helps improve usability!

[Switch account](#)

Not shared

1. I think I would like to use this system frequently.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree

3. I thought the system was easy to use.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

4. I think I would need technical support to use this system.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

5. I found the various functions were well integrated.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in the system.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

7. I would imagine most people would learn to use it quickly.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

8. I found the system very cumbersome to use.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

9. I felt very confident using the system.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

10. I needed to learn a lot before using the system.

- 1: Strongly Disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neutral (Neither Agree nor Disagree)
- 4: Agree
- 5: Strongly Agree

Submit

Clear form

Appendix D

User experience Questionnaire Survey Form

Enhancing User Experience and Accessibility in Digital Archives of Music Cultural Heritage

Thanks for joining the survey! Your feedback will help make digital music heritage archives easier to use and more enjoyable. Just share your thoughts based on your experience! 😊

[Switch account](#)

Not shared

1. Does the design look good and attractive?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

2. Do you enjoy using this system?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral

3. Were tasks completed quickly?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

4. Does the system accomplish goals efficiently?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

5. Do you feel confident when navigating?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

6. Is the system consistent and predictable?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

7. Is it easy to learn to use the system?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

8. Are features clearly explained or intuitive?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

9. Is the system exciting to use?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

10. Does it motivate you to explore features?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

11. Does the system feel innovative?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

12. Are the features creative and unique?

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral

Appendix E

Post-Test Interview Guide

Post-Test Interview Guide: Evaluating the User Experience of the Digital Music Archive *A qualitative feedback session to assess usability, accessibility, and engagement*

1. Overall Usability and Experience

Q1: *What was your overall experience using the digital archive?
(This allows participants to freely express their general impressions.)*

Q2: *Were there any specific features you found particularly helpful or enjoyable? Why?
(Identifies strengths and user-preferred elements of the system.)*

2. Ease of Use and Learnability

Q3: *How easy or difficult was it to learn how to use the system?
(Explores learnability and onboarding experience.)*

Q4: *Were there any moments where you felt lost or unsure about what to do next? If so, can you describe them?
(Reveals potential usability issues, especially in navigation and workflow.)*

3. Accessibility and Inclusivity

Q5: *Did you experience any difficulties accessing or interacting with the system based on your personal needs
(e.g., readability, navigation, accessibility tools)?
(Assesses how well the system accommodates users with different abilities.)*

Q6: *What improvements would you suggest to make the system more inclusive and accessible for a wider range
of users?
(Encourages recommendations for improving accessibility features.)*

4. Engagement and User Satisfaction

Q7: *How engaging did you find the system? Were there any features that made the experience more enjoyable
or frustrating?
(Identifies how well the system keeps users interested.)*

Q8: *Would you return to use this archive in the future? Why or why not?
(Evaluates long-term user engagement and retention potential.)*

5. Areas for Improvement

Q9: *If you could change or improve one aspect of the system, what would it be and why?
(Prioritizes the most critical improvement areas from the user's perspective.)*

Q10: *Do you have any additional feedback or suggestions that weren't covered in the survey?
(Allows participants to share insights that may not have been captured in previous questions.)*

Appendix F

Additional Lower-Fidelity Prototyping

1-1

login page

A hand-drawn wireframe of a login page. At the top right, there is a close button 'X'. Below it is the site name 'Rw. Music - Archive' with a logo consisting of a circle with an 'X' inside. The main heading is 'login' with a person icon. There are two input fields: 'Email' with the placeholder 'Enter your email' and an '@' icon, and 'Password' with the placeholder 'Enter your password' and an eye icon. Below the password field are two links: '1.3 forgot password' and '1.2 Dont have account'. At the bottom right is a 'Login' button.

2-factor Authentication page

1.5

One-Time password

We have sent a one-time password to your registered email, check your inbox or spam to get the code.

One-time password

Continue

[Back to sign in](#)